

D3.2 Portfolio of improved ecological criteria to be applied in systemic biodiversity protection and restoration

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Abstract	<p>In order to achieve the effective designation and management of area-based management tools (ABMTs) and ecologically coherent networks of those, the functional roles of species, communities and the whole ecosystem functioning should be included in decision-making processes addressing the conservation of the ecological status of marine areas. Ecological functions and ecosystem functioning, however, have so far not been fully incorporated into management or policy, mainly due to data constraints. Deliverable 3.1 provided an analysis of the existing scientific literature addressing this issue and suggesting relevant criteria and methods for the inclusion of ecological functioning and related dimensions into the design and management of area-based protection measures. The information obtained was used in Deliverable 3.2 to provide a list of criteria focusing on functional aspects and attributes across different levels of biological organization (from individuals to ecosystem). The integration with existing conservation criteria (focusing mainly on structural aspects of ecosystems) will boost the effectiveness of marine conservation. Biological traits, functional</p>

diversity, trophic ecology, food web functioning and connectivity were the broad categories of criteria that were proposed or already considered in the literature for the prioritization, designation and management of ABMTs and their networks. In this deliverable, based on the best knowledge gained from the systematic literature review performed in Deliverable 3.1, the potential applicability of functional criteria, associated methods and metrics to evaluate them, and data availability are analyzed and discussed. A portfolio of improved ecological criteria is provided to be integrated into the ecological module (ESE 1) which will be part of the wider Ecological-Socio-Economic management (ESE) framework that will be co-developed in Task 4.4. The aim of this portfolio of improved criteria is to effectively catalyze (throughout the integration into the ESE model) actions for systematic biodiversity protection and effective conservation and restoration of the ecological status of marine ecosystems, generally addressing European seas, but with a particular focus on the application in the test sites of the MSP4BIO project.

Keywords

portfolio, functional criteria, ecosystem function, ecosystem process, conservation, restoration, area-based conservation

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Acronyms

ABMTs - Area-based Management Tools

BTA - Biological Traits Analysis

CBD - Convention on Biological Diversity

CEA - Cumulative Effects Assessment

CC - Climate Change

CMS - Connectivity Modeling System

DAPSTOM - Integrated Database and Portal for Fish Stomach Records

DEVOTES Project - DEvelopment Of innovative Tools for understanding marine biodiversity and assessing good Environmental Status

DFG - Derelict Fishing Gears

DFO - Fisheries and Oceans Canada

DST - Decision Support Tool

EBSAs - Ecologically or Biologically Significant Marine Areas

eDNA - Environmental DNA (Deoxyribonucleic acid)

EMODnet - European Marine Observation and Data Network

EwE - Ecopath with Ecosim

FD - Functional diversity

FITC - Fishery-Induced trophic cascades

FRic - Functional richness index

GBIF - Global Biodiversity Information Facility

HD - Habitats Directive

HELCOM - Helsinki Commission (Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission)

IMMA - Important Marine Mammal Area

IMO - International Maritime Organisation

IUCN - International Union for the Conservation of Nature

ILTER - Long Term Ecological Research

LTRANS - Larval TRANSport Lagrangian model

MiCO - Migratory Connectivity in the Ocean

MPAs - Marine Protected Areas

MSFD - Marine Strategy Framework Directive

NASA - National Aeronautics and Space Administration

NGOs - Non-Governmental Organisations

NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration

OBIS - Ocean Biodiversity Information System

OECMs - Other Effective area-based Conservation Measures

OSPAR - Oslo and Paris Conventions

PAs - Protected Areas

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*PU*s - *Planning Units*

PCA - *Principal Component Analysis*

POSE Framework - *Precocial–Opportunistic–Survivor–Episodic Framework*

PSSA - *Particularly Sensitive Sea Areas*

SCAR - *Sequence Characterized Amplified Region*

SST - *Sea Surface Temperature*

SPR - *Spawning Potential Ratio*

UNEP - *United Nations Environment Programme*

UNEP-WCMC - *United Nations Environment Programme World Conservation Monitoring Centre*

UNGA - *United Nations General Assembly*

*VME*s - *Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems*

WFD- *Water Framework Directive*

WMOP - *Western Mediterranean Operational Forecasting System*

WoRMS - *World Register of Marine Species*

Glossary

Area-based Management Tools (ABMTs): ABMTs are instruments that entail “*the implementation of a system of rights and duties in a particular management area, under the responsibility of a designated authority, and ABMTs tend to afford high levels of protection*” (definition from Gissi et al. 2022, based on UNGA 2007; Prior et al. 2010). ABMTs include Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) and Other Effective area-based Conservation Measures (OECMs).

Biological organizational levels: biological organization levels refers to the classification of biological systems in a hierarchical manner according to their level of complexity (e.g. from molecules to single organisms, from species to communities and ecosystems). The level of biological organization has been defined by several studies, such as for example in Scheffers et al. (2016), to address climate change (CC) impacts and responses on different biological systems.

Criterion/criteria: in the context of the present document, a criterion is defined as a standard or principle for prioritizing and managing conservation areas and designing and evaluating the effectiveness of conservation measures. Some examples of criteria can be the protection of feeding grounds for endangered predators, areas/habitats essential for the development of the life cycle of keystone species, or the maintenance of genetic diversity hotspots essential to ensure adaptation in the context of CC, among others.

Ecologically or Biologically Significant Marine Areas (EBSAs): EBSAs are defined as geographically or oceanographically discrete areas that need protection since they provide important services to one or more species/populations of an ecosystem or the ecosystem as a whole, compared to other surrounding areas that meet the EBSA criteria (defined in 2008, during the ninth meeting of the Conference of the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity, COP 9). There are seven scientific criteria to identify EBSAs: (1) uniqueness or rarity, (2) special importance for the life history of species, (3) importance for threatened, endangered or declining species and/or habitats, (4) vulnerability, fragility, sensitivity, slow recovery, (5) biological productivity, (6) biological diversity, and (7) naturalness. Further details can be found in CBD (2009) and Ardron et al. (2009).” In contrast to other ABMTs, EBSAs are not legally binding (Roe et al. 2022).

Ecosystem function and functioning: ecosystem functioning refers to the set of ecological and biogeochemical processes that defines the cycle of matter and flow of energy in marine ecosystems (de Groot et al. 2002).

Ecosystem process: ecosystem processes are those biological, physical, and geochemical processes responsible for the flow of energy and cycle of matter in ecosystems (modified from GEOBON, <https://geobon.org/ebvs/working-groups/ecosystem-function/>). Ecosystem processes can be seen as components of ecosystems that interact in complex and diverse ways that contribute to and sustain

biodiversity. Processes may also act as selective forces to which particular species constantly adapt. Collectively, **ecosystem processes** produce organic matter, transfer carbon and nutrients, and drive habitat formation, among others.

Functional diversity (FD): functional diversity is a diversity metric based on organismal traits (attributes and functions), -that influence one or more aspects of the functioning of an ecosystem (e.g its dynamics, stability, productivity, nutrient balance, and other aspects) (Mouchet et al. 2010).

Functional group: a functional group is a collection of functionally similar species with a similar functional role in a system regardless of their taxonomic affinity (from Table S2 supplement material in Bellwood et al. 2019).

Functional trait: functional traits are features measurable at the individual level, without reference to the environment or any other level of organization, and which impact fitness indirectly via their effects on growth, reproduction and survival, where trait is considered a variable measured on an organism at any scale, from gene to whole organism and which can be scaled up from individuals to genotype, population, species, or community (Volaire et al., 2020 and literature therein). Examples of functional traits are total length (category body size), trophic level (category trophic Index), gregariousness (level of occurrence as solitary, couple, group of individuals) and diel (diurnal/nocturnal) activity pattern (category behavior), preferred substrate (hard, soft) and complexity preference (category habitat use), thermal affinity based on occupied temperature distribution (category physiology).

Indicator: an indicator is a direct measurement or a proxy of relevant biotic or abiotic components/processes used to implement and assess criteria.

Life-history trait: life history traits are a set of events experienced and strategies followed by the organism of a given species that defined their survival and reproductive success throughout their life cycle. Life history strategies evolve by natural selection, and they represent an "optimization" of trade-offs between growth, survival, and reproduction. Examples of **life history traits** are: age at first reproductive event, reproductive lifespan and aging, number and size of offspring, age at first reproductive event, reproductive lifespan and aging, etc. (Stearns, 2000).

Marine Protected Area (MPA): MPAs defined by the IUCN are clearly defined areas, recognized, dedicated, and managed, through legal or other effective means, to achieve the long-term conservation of nature with associated ecosystem services and cultural values. (IUCN-WCPA, 2008).

Significant areas: significant areas host an outstanding proportion of biodiversity (e.g., a species, habitat, or ecosystem), this definition is based on the definition of 'significant' by IUCN (IUCN 2016).

Biological traits: biological traits refer to a wide range of characteristics found in organisms, including their physical, biochemical, and ecological attributes. These traits define an organism's role in its environment, affecting how it responds to its surroundings and influences ecosystem processes. Examples of traits include physical features like body size, morphology, and shoot density, as well as behavioral aspects such as motility and reproductive strategies.

Trait-based approaches: trait-based approaches are defined in ecological research as any method that focuses on individual traits rather than species, could provide this

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common framework (McGill et al. 2006, Kremer et al. 2017). These approaches emerged from terrestrial ecology when attributes at the individual level, initially used to describe ecosystem function based on elements common to multiple species, were considered to gather individuals into functional groups (i.e., “plant functional types”) based on their physical, phylogenetic, and phenological characteristics, rather than on their taxonomy (e.g., species).

Executive Summary

In order to achieve the effective designation and management of area-based management tools (ABMTs) and ecologically coherent networks of those, the functional roles of species, communities and the whole ecosystem functioning should be included in decision-making processes addressing the conservation of the ecological status of marine areas. Ecological functions and ecosystem functioning, however, have so far not been fully incorporated into management or policy, mainly due to data constraints. Deliverable 3.1 provided an analysis of the existing scientific literature addressing this issue and suggesting relevant criteria and methods for the inclusion of ecological functioning and related dimensions into the design and management of area-based protection measures. The information obtained was used in Deliverable 3.2 to provide a list of criteria focusing on functional aspects and attributes across different levels of biological organization (from individuals to ecosystem). The integration with existing conservation criteria (focusing mainly on structural aspects of ecosystems) will boost the effectiveness of marine conservation. Biological traits, functional diversity, trophic ecology, food web functioning and connectivity were the broad categories of criteria that were proposed or already considered in the literature for the prioritization, designation and management of ABMTs and their networks. In this deliverable, based on the best knowledge gained from the systematic literature review performed in Deliverable 3.1, the potential applicability of functional criteria, associated methods and metrics to evaluate them, and data availability are analyzed and discussed. A portfolio of improved ecological criteria is provided to be integrated into the ecological module (ESE 1) which will be part of the wider Ecological-Socio-Economic management (ESE) framework that will be co-developed in Task 4.4. The aim of this portfolio of improved criteria is to effectively catalyze (throughout the integration into the ESE model) actions for systematic biodiversity protection and effective conservation and restoration of the ecological status of marine ecosystems, generally addressing European seas, but with a particular focus on the application in the test sites of the MSP4BIO project.

1. Introduction

Effective conservation and restoration strategies must ensure that species remain not just extant but are also able to maintain key roles in species interactions and in the maintenance of communities and ecosystem processes. Indeed, ecosystem functioning, the set of processes that biotic and abiotic components perform within ecosystems, is becoming universally recognized as a more effective way to conserve ecosystems and sustain the flow of the services they provide (de Groot et al. 2002, Bennett et al. 2009, Klein et al. 2009, Magris et al. 2014, Watson et al. 2016).

Functional aspects of species and communities (e.g. the diversity of life histories and functional groups, i.e. groups of species that perform similar functions in an ecosystem) have shown to improve resilience to climatic and human perturbations (Hilborn et al. 2003), mediate ecosystem-level processes and support the healthy functioning of marine ecosystems (Levin and Levin 2002, Duffy et al. 2007). Functional processes include intra- and inter-specific interactions and movements of organisms, primary productivity, carbon (C) flow through food webs, hydrological processes, among others.

In recent years, marine conservation has received an increasing attention, and several studies have attempted to assess the effectiveness of implemented measures to achieve conservation targets set by management objectives (e.g. Giakoumi et al. 2018, Grorud-Colvert et al. 2021, Pendleton et al. 2018). These targets are generally defined and evaluated based on criteria related to the conservation status of single species, the use of taxonomic diversity indices, and the physical characteristics of habitats (Miatta et al. 2021). However, little attention has been devoted to identifying and measuring functional aspects that can be used to design new Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) or redefine existing ones.

Moreover, no effort has been made so far to systematically screen, assess and improve existing approaches and criteria to generate a coherent framework that explicitly considers functional diversity and ecosystem functioning in marine conservation. In addition there is a strong need to provide protocols that guide the implementation of functional dimensions into management or policy under different data realities (Brodie et al. 2018).

Deliverable 3.2 uses and improves the available scientific information on functional aspects of marine ecosystems gathered from the systematic review performed in Deliverable 3.1. This systematic review provided the bases for listing the functional aspects/attributes that will be critical to maintain and, therefore, prioritize areas for conservation that support species and ecosystems providing these functions. The main aim of Deliverable 3.2 (D3.2) is to provide a portfolio of novel, potential **functional criteria** that have not been systematically considered so far but have been shown to exert explicit

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and positive effects on biodiversity and ecosystems, and are indeed considered more appropriate conservation targets to maintain the integrity and functioning of marine ecosystems. In this document, a criterion is intended as a standard principle for prioritizing and managing conservation areas and designing and evaluating the effectiveness of conservation measures. Functional criteria will contribute to advance those principles, in addition to the currently used criteria (mainly structural ones, screened in Task 2.2 of Work Package 2, WP2) for area-based management tools (ABMTs). Functional criteria are screened in order to be applicable for MPAs and Ecologically or Biologically Significant Marine Areas (EBSAs) and for the identification and improvement of MPA networks (e.g., enlargement and networking) and considering species and habitats listed as a priority for protection on environmental directives (e.g., Habitats Directive 92/43/EEC, among others) and those recognized as vulnerable and threatened. The identified criteria will be successively proposed in addition to the criteria currently adopted (defined in WP2) in order to improve the efficacy of prioritization and conservation measures. Criteria will flow into Task 3.3. (T3.3) to feed the ecological module ESE1 and to effectively catalyze actions for systematic biodiversity protection and effective restoration, and to support nature-based solutions. Here we present a general framework for application of improved criteria in European seas, based on functional aspects rather than structural ones. A comparative screening between results of T2.1 and data needed to feed the functional criteria will indicate the general availability of data for the new criteria and identify proxy data if necessary. In addition, to showcase their potential applicability, selected criteria will be addressed on the main environmental features and management questions of some of the six MSP4BIO test sites, when applicable.

2. Methodology: from D3.1 to 3.2

Here we provide information on how results obtained from the systematic review detailed in D3.1 were used to inform D3.2, i.e, the construction of a portfolio of functional criteria for marine conservation. In particular our analysis started from the information extracted from the selected literature, relative to functional criteria (column Query 1 of the extraction of information spreadsheet, see D3.1). The query was the following: on which functional criteria is the study focusing on? Indicate and define in a few lines the target criteria/attributes/process mentioned in the article (criteria that refer to processes and properties of ecosystems and their components that relate to functioning, from ecosystem level to species level).

The terms related to functional criteria were harmonized and the frequencies with which they were reported was calculated and graphically displayed using a word cloud approach (Fig 9. in D3.1, Fig. 1 of this Deliverable).

Results of the systematic literature screening indicated that functional diversity, life history traits, trophic interactions, food webs structures, foraging and refuge areas and growth were the most cited terms related to criteria. Connectivity, although representing a fundamental criteria category to be inserted in the portfolio, was not analyzed for the review exercise as it has been largely documented in exhaustive and recently published reviews. A general description of this criterion as well as the rationale for not including it in the extraction exercise has been discussed in D3.1.

Following this, the identified categories of criteria were classified on the bases of their application at different biological organizational levels, i.e., the basis of how living organisms are classified in a hierarchical and orderly manner according to their level of complexity (from molecules to single organisms, from species to communities and ecosystems).

The availability of data for each cluster was analysed by extracting and counting relevant datasets, data platforms, tools, and models from the data availability table produced by T2.1 (in WP2). The resulting lists of datasets per cluster were made available to all MSP4BIO partners in a shared Excel spreadsheet. For clusters in which data availability was low, suggestions were made on data that could be used as a proxy or methods of searching for or collecting relevant data. Functional criteria were also cross-checked with criteria in use (from T2.2, WP2) to find potential links and synergies.

2.2 Applicability of criteria for conservation purposes

Information collected and extracted from the scientific literature was used to describe criteria applicability in terms of conservation goals. For each criteria category, we provided examples of indices, metrics, type of data or data proxies needed to evaluate a specific criterion, and when available we provided information on their use or potential use in decision support tools/models, etc. This deliverable lists available methods to study/assess functional criteria and discusses, whenever possible, the potential limitations of methodological approaches. The aim of providing this information is to support decision-makers and managers to evaluate what data and methods are needed in order to include functional aspects into conservation.

In practice, for each of the collected criteria, the following information were provided:

1. a general definition of the criterion,
2. how it has been used, or could be used from an ecological perspective (in terms of the conservation goals that the criterion addresses),
3. how the criteria is evaluated/measured (method),
4. how it can be applied (through indexes and metrics),
5. what data is needed (i.e., data and data proxies).

Regarding the criteria linked to abiotic attributes of ecosystems, we decided not to consider them in the frame of T3.1 and only discuss them in the frame of Task 3.2 (D3.2.) since these factors are more strictly associated with CCs.

The above work was mainly based on the selected scientific literature screened in the systematic review integrated with scientific and technical reports and other gray literature that was not taken into consideration during the systematic review.

3. Results

3.1 Criteria clustering

Terms/keywords were clustered into four main groups (biological/ecological traits, trophic ecology, functional diversity and connectivity) (Fig. 2). The additional cluster 'Others' was composed mainly of terms related to abiotic criteria. The overlapping areas contain terms shared by clusters, i.e. those that refer to or inform more than one criterion.

The application of criteria at different biological levels of organization are categorized as:

- Biological traits: defined at the organismal level, but generally applied at the species (e.g. to define species sensitivity, vulnerability, recovery to stressors), community or ecosystem level (used to evaluate functional diversity which is related to ecosystem health, i.e. how biological entities respond and adapt to an environment).
- Functional diversity: estimated at the community level.
- Trophic ecology: defined at the level of organic material or at species/group of species level based on the specific feeding mode and food sources. It extends to the community and ecosystem level as trophic ecology implies the cycling of matter in an environment.
- Connectivity - mainly includes criteria applicable from molecules (genes/ organic matter) up to ecosystems, as it takes into consideration active and passive movements of animals, propagules and materials within and among ecosystems.

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Figure 2. Clustering of terms related to broad categories of functional criteria. Clusters (circles) of criteria are represented in different colors and criteria terms that link/inform more than one criteria group are placed in the overlapping portions of the clusters.

3.2 Description of functional criteria

Here, for each of the main screened ecological criteria we provide a clear definition, a description of the rationale of their use in guiding the prioritization of areas from an ecological perspective (how the criteria respond to conservation questions/goals), the design of ABMTs, and the construction of networks. In addition, for each criteria we provide information on how criteria can be applied providing insights on the methodologies, metrics and indices that are more commonly used for their assessment, and data-type requirements.

3.2.1 Biological traits

3.2.1.1 Biological traits – definition

Generally, “*biological*” traits represent *morphological, biochemical, physiological, structural, phenological, behavioral, and ecological characteristics of organisms, whether individuals or species* (Diaz and Cabido 2001). Attributes such as motility, body size, life span, trophic mode, reproduction modalities, and habitat characterize the ecological roles that organisms play (Diaz and Cabido 2001, Violle et al. 2014), the interactions between individuals and species and with the environment (Lefcheck et al. 2015). Traits are therefore useful to infer the responses and adaptation of organisms to their environment and the effects of organisms on ecosystem processes (Violle et al. 2007, Nock et al. 2016).

Therefore, functional traits include the characteristics of an organism that are considered relevant to its response to the environment and/or its effects on ecosystem functioning. Examples of functional traits are morphological, behavioral and physiological characteristics such as body size, motility and dispersal mode, capacity for symbiotic fixation of nitrogen etc. (Diaz and Cabido, 2001). Functional traits not only help derive individual strategies, but also to connect them to functions at organizational levels higher than those of the species such as the community or ecosystem level.

Life history traits are more referred to the life-history of organisms (or measurable demographic characteristics of populations) that have a direct impact on two key aspects of their fitness: their ability to survive and their capacity for reproduction. They include phenotypic characteristics that affect fitness, e.g. size at birth, age or size at maturity, and the sex ratio of offspring, and age- or stage-specific growth rates, age at first reproduction, reproduction strategy and lifespan of an organism etc. (Stearns 2000). All these features are subject to natural selection and are thus heritable to some degree.

3.2.1.2 Biological traits - application to ABMTs prioritization, design and monitoring

Trait-based indicators can complement, rather than replace, the conventional biodiversity and habitat-based indicators informing criteria classically used in marine conservation. When creating a new ABMT, traits and methodologies should be chosen based on the fundamental ecological questions that define conservation priorities, which could relate to assemblage functioning, the presence and impacts of human activities, or both. Traits based on organisms feeding, behavior, response, and effect can provide insights into various aspects of ecosystem dynamics (Miatta et al. 2021).

Traits can be useful to: (a) identify conservation priorities by assessing and predicting the **sensitivity and vulnerability of species and communities to human-made impacts and CC, as well as forecasting species extinction risks and evaluating community resilience**. Trait-based vulnerability assessments can provide improved information for prioritizing actions for species conservation, whether focused on a species that has different and multiple stressors operating at different life-history stages or on determining which management actions would secure the most threatened species (Butt et al 2021 and literature therein). Extinction risk can be predicted by applying the same principles used to gauge sensitivity, both individual and species traits can help predict the risk of populations and species going extinct. This predictive capability offers the advantage of identifying vulnerable species and detecting changes caused by disturbances before local extinctions occur and guiding in setting conservation priorities (e.g., Cardillo et al. 2006, Van Kleunen and Richardson 2007, Cooke et al. 2019). For instance, Cooke et al. (2019) used the biological traits of over 15,000 terrestrial mammals and birds to assess their current ecological strategies and predict changes over the next century. Their predictions suggest that mammal and bird species will shift towards becoming smaller, faster-lived, highly prolific, and insect-eating generalists (Miatta et al., 2021).

The assessments of species vulnerability using the trait-based approach **for protected area design** can allow for much more precise targeting of protection, compared to those based on ecosystem vulnerability, thus avoiding potential conflicts over where to locate conservation areas. Moreover, when stressors cross ecosystem and political boundaries (e.g., land-based runoff), species-level assessments can guide co-management of stressors in relation to the affected species (Butt et al. 2021 and literature therein).

Management actions accounting for life history traits of threatened species can lead to their recovery, and eventually to resilient populations that are better able to withstand further environmental changes.

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Life history traits that have previously been used by researchers as a proxy of resistance to disturbance; for example, maximum body size (length), body growth rate, longevity, age or length at sexual maturity, and rate of natural mortality are the life history parameters that have been shown to correlate with vulnerability (Absesamis et al 2014, and literature therein). McLean et al. (2019) showed that sensitivity to climatic disturbances depends on communities' initial traits' structure, i.e. dominance of species with climatically vulnerable traits (e.g small, fast-growing pelagics/corallivores) while communities with higher trait redundancy were more resistant. This study was one of the first to use extensive data to show that biological traits can predict how disturbances will affect biodiversity and ecosystems across different environments and species. Life history traits are indeed valuable criteria for evaluating species sensitivity or adaptability to climate and predicting current and future CC effects and again for guiding PAs' design (Miatta et al. 2021, Albouy et al. 2020). Traits such as habitat specialization, environmental tolerances, reliance on environmental cues or interactions with other species that CC may disrupt, rarity, limited dispersal ability, and a restricted capacity for evolution and adaptation are among the key factors. By combining information on species sensitivity with predictions of CC effects in different regions, we can determine population vulnerability and prioritize conservation areas. For example, Albouy et al. (2020) used a trait-based approach to assess the vulnerability of marine mammals to global warming under high and low greenhouse gas emission scenarios. This was done by evaluation indexes of sensitivity and exposure to temperature (i.e. projecting the future magnitude of warming in the species range). A trait-based approach was applied to assess the risk of ninety marine Mediterranean species threatened by CC, through the combination of species' exposure to increased sea temperature and intrinsic vulnerability (Chatzimentor et al. 2023).

Traits have also been used to spot the difference between changes caused by human or environmental pressures and random variations in natural communities. This is because when there's a disturbance it often reduces the number of species with specific traits. (b) Facilitate spatial planning by **pinpointing new diversity hotspots, identifying functionally critical areas** by generating maps that showcase functional diversity and ecosystem functioning. Integrating individual traits across various species to describe communities represents the most precise means of characterizing functional diversity and elucidating functional processes (Frid et al. 2008; Miatta et al. 2021). The traits approach can be applied in various contexts, including the design of large areas covering multiple biogeographic regions, to establish conservation priorities, and the monitoring of community development following protection and exposure to disturbance events. This approach can be especially valuable for large-scale environmental policies implemented across diverse geographic regions, where variations in species composition might

otherwise complicate traditional, species-centric assessments (Bremner et al. 2003; Frid et al. 2008; Villnäs et al. in 2018).

(c) Contribute to the development of **monitoring programs designed to detect early signs of recovery after the establishment of protected areas (PAs)**. For instance, trait-based approaches enable the identification of species responsible for crucial ecological processes, thus allowing for the tracing of function-related changes back to alterations in the biota, which can, in turn, be linked to human activities that management measures can address (Frid et al. 2008). Monitoring of PAs that involves the ongoing assessment of the biological traits of species over time can effectively trace the impacts of management interventions. When compared with a control site, this approach allows for the attribution of protection from other variables that also change over time, such as temperature increases (Bates et al. 2014). Trait-based methodologies indeed can furnish information about alterations in the functionality of biological communities over time and confirm whether protective measures yield positive effects on their functioning (de Bello et al. in 2010 and Vandewalle et al. 2010). Therefore, when necessary, they also allow for swift and adaptive management responses. Interestingly, some studies have also tried to determine which life history traits could favor or boost species invasiveness as traits can be determinant for the success of different invasion stages (e.g. spreading, full establishment, Casties and Briski 2019).

Biological traits analysis (BTA) has been successfully used to **describe ecological functioning** in marine benthic systems. BTA uses a number of biological characteristics expressed by the taxa present as indicators of key ecosystem functions (Frid et al., 2008). These were chosen by experts who concluded that BTA represented the best tool currently available for quantifying ecological functioning and agreed on 10 key ecological functions delivered by marine benthic communities. Also, these experts identified twenty-four biological functions as proxies or indices for these ten functions (Frid et al. 2008).

In addition, it is worth mentioning that Fisheries and Oceans Canada (DFO 2004) and the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD 2009) developed separate criteria for the identification of EBSAs. DFO has defined the fitness consequences: areas where important life history activities (e.g., reproduction) that strongly affect the fitness of a species or population take place. One of the CBD 2009 EBSA criteria consists of designing areas of special importance for life-history stages of species, i.e. the areas required for a population to survive and thrive (e.g., breeding or nursery grounds, spawning areas, migratory species habitat). Other criteria (at international level, sea basin level, and European level) have also been identified that consider life history stages in D2.2 (WP2).

3.2.1.3 Biological traits - methods

Despite the potential usefulness of biological traits in conservation efforts, there are still relatively few instances where trait-based methods have been employed to shape conservation strategies and guide the design of PAs. Analyses should encompass multiple biological traits and diverse taxa to offer a comprehensive view of ecological functioning and the effects of natural and human-induced factors on biological communities. A careful approach should evaluate which traits are more indicative of a specific conservation goal and decrease as much as possible traits redundancy. Different traits may also influence different ecosystem processes. Therefore, managing biodiversity based on multi-traits diversity indices can support multiple ecosystem functions and associated benefits. Furthermore, if appropriate and feasible, analyses should account for intraspecific traits variability. In some cases, easily measurable morphological traits can serve as cost-effective and time-efficient proxies of assessing diversity for conservation purposes, particularly when distinguishing between taxa is challenging, as seen in sponge or coral reef ecosystems where morphological features relate directly to habitat complexity. Lastly, the chosen traits and analytical methods should balance sensitivity and effectiveness in describing assemblages, functions, and responses to impacts with ease of measurement and interpretation (Miatta et al, 2021). In reality, there is no single methodology that can precisely measure the extent of "function" that biological assemblages deliver, or the amount required to ensure human well-being (Miatta et al. 2021) Nevertheless, the potential to generalize results from trait-based analyses across similar habitats in various regions means that biological traits can help address challenges in comparing vulnerability assessments, which often span different spatial scales, as highlighted by Vandewalle et al. (2010).

In the study by Frid et al. (2008), the BTA feasibility was tested for benthic communities of Eddystone Reef (Cornwall, UK), using the following 28 biological traits as indices (following the study by Bremner et al. 2006): 1) maximum size; 2) maximum growth rate; 3) longevity; 4) time to maturity; 5) reproductive method; 6) fecundity; 7) propagule dispersal; 8) body design; 9) living habitat; 10) living location/environmental position; 11) exposure potential; 12) degree of flexibility; 13) degree of attachment; 14) strength of attachment; 15) resource capture method; 16) food type; 17) energy transfer efficiency; 18) tissue components; 19) defense strategy; 20) movement method; 21) mobility; 22) water column migration; 23) horizontal migration; 24) intra-specific sociability; 25) predictability of dynamics; 26) recruitment variability/success; 27) biogenic habitat provision; 28) scale of habitat provision. This approach allowed for an improved designation of PA boundaries through identification of organisms' functional roles and crucial ecosystem functions using a centered (covariance) PCA and co-inertia analyses. The PCA allows for scoring of differences of ecological structures among benthic

communities and graphically presenting the range of ecological characteristics of these communities (e.g., range of the type of sea bottom). The co-inertia analysis was used to examine the differences of ecological functioning among the sampled stations in the study and similarly to PCA, scores these differences. However, the co-inertia analysis combines two types of data: the abundance of taxa from each study location and their biological traits.

Modeling species traits can have some advantages compared to those species-based, which are usually complex, difficult to parameterize and often produce outcomes that cannot be generalized to other species. Trait-based models indeed require less parameterization effort, can be scaled-up, and produce results that can be generalizable for other systems and be used to fill gaps in species knowledge (Zacharova et al., 2019). An example of how to infer species relative vulnerability from modeling based on traits approach is given by Butt et al. (2022). These authors estimated the vulnerability of a given species to a given stressor as a function of its sensitivity, e.g. related to tolerance limits and specializations, adaptive capacity, and potential exposure based on species-level traits and habitat preferences. Traits linked to species sensitivity and adaptation capacity were selected on the basis of experts' knowledge and literature information. A traits-stressors matrix was built by assigning for each threat a level of vulnerability to stressors. The matrix was built considering only the direct effect of a stressor without considering additive or synergistic impacts of multiple stressors. Successively, the matrix was used to model vulnerability and assign scores (Butt et al. 2021, Fig. 3). The framework provides an essential step toward the development of cumulative impact maps on a species level (which is often the scale at which managers operate) to inform conservation and management.

Figure 3. Evaluation of species vulnerability based on traits linked to sensitivity and adaptation to stressors: major steps consist in the development of the traits framework

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based on expert judgment and literature review, on the traits-stressors matrix and model originating the vulnerability scores (Figure 1 in Butt et al. 2021).

Another interesting methodological approach is the one proposed by Kindsvater et al. (2016). These authors developed the POSE (Precocial–Opportunistic–Survivor–Episodic) framework connecting characteristic life histories (defined as Precocial, Opportunistic, Survivor, and Episodic) to their compensatory capacity, i.e. the ability of a population to withstand various types of mortality. This is based on the concept that density-dependent regulation of population dynamics depends on the life-history traits of a population or species (e.g. when the birth/ individuals or juvenile survival rates increase when the population decreases). These authors suggested that considering where a species’ life history traits falls on the POSE spectrum can provide support to detect which populations or species are at greatest risk of extinction and suggest management actions leading to recovery, and eventually to resilient populations that are better able to withstand further environmental change (Fig 4, from Figure 2 in Kindsvater et al. 2016).

Figure 4. Figure illustrates the extremes of the position of different species to the POSE categories. Position derives from the combination between life-history traits, juvenile mortality and adult mortality, and the capacity of species to compensate (calculated as spawning potential ratio, SPR) the pressure of fishing. Each category reports a set of reproductive traits, body size, growth, age at maturity, and lifespan that coevolve according to size-independent juvenile mortality and adult mortality. As an example, for extremes, in the “survivor” species: the increase of juvenile and adult survival with size evolves in association to a reduction in the number of offspring and increased parental care. If adult mortality is also low, selection favors increased investment per offspring, long lifespans, and large body sizes resulting in species slow growth and few, relatively large offspring, and parental care. As such the compensatory capacity of these species is low and they are highly likely to be threatened by anthropogenic and climate impacts. On the other extreme are the “precocial” species with low juvenile mortality and high adult mortality associated with large offspring and early maturity and having a high compensatory capacity. This category is associated with parental care, a high density-independent mortality of juveniles, and large numbers of offspring instead of increased investment per offspring (Figure 2 in Kindsvater et al. 2016).

Therefore, spatial management will be most effective in the locations that contribute the most to subsequent generations (e.g., those with high relative fitness), if protected individuals are near maturity, if they have high survival during their time in that habitat, or if a large proportion of the population uses the area.

In their study, Chatzimentor et al. (2023) used species traits analysis to assess the risk for threatened (critically endangered, endangered, and vulnerable) marine species of the Mediterranean Sea to climate warming. They provided a step-by-step methodology: (1) assessed selected traits that reflect species vulnerability to climatic impacts, (2) estimated the species' exposure levels to increased temperatures; (3) assessed the level of risk of species to increased temperatures, combining their vulnerability and exposure. They then translated species' climate risk into a spatial risk assessment for the Mediterranean Sea and delineated critical areas that host most of the high climate risk species. Moreover, by estimating the spatial overlap of high climate risk areas with Mediterranean marine protected areas (MPAs) they detected potential opportunities for the conservation of high climate risk species.

Vulnerability, sensitivity indices based on biological traits can be used in combination with climate velocity (a simple metric that describes the speed and direction of climate movement at any point in space) to trace projection of climate risks (Burrows et al. 2014, Pinsky et al. 2013, Sunday et al. 2015). Such methods can help to identify species that

could be at risk in future CC scenarios. All these issues will be detailed in Task 3.2 (D3.3) of the MSP4BIO project.

3.2.1.4 Biological traits - metrics and indices

Metrics rooted in biological traits provide a common measure of diversity that can be applied universally across species and environments (Vandewalle et al. 2010). This enables comparisons of functional biodiversity across different geographical locations (Statzner et al. 2001, Hodgson et al. 2005). While the ecosystem-based management considers species functions and inter-species interactions (in comparison to traditional fishing approaches where species are considered in isolation), the use of trait-based metrics is still in development. Using metrics based on biological traits offers an alternative perspective through the traditional application of species richness, evenness or other diversity matrices based on counts or proportions, making the trait-based approach more applicable to a wide variety of spatial scales. This has an advantage as variation occurs at many different levels (e.g. inter and intra population, species, location) that may be taken into account to a greater extent by using a traits-based approach rather than the conventional indices.

Cooke et al. (2019) used six traits to compute functional redundancy (similarity of species roles) and functional dispersion index (breadth of roles across taxa) for birds and mammals across ecoregions (Diaz and Cabido 2001, Mouillot et al. 2013). Functional redundancy was evaluated by binning traits with the Sturges algorithm (i.e. data were divided into classes based on the sample size and distribution of values across each trait). The functional dispersion was generated by computing pairwise dissimilarities of transformed traits using the Gower dissimilarity matrix. Then in order to identify regions with unique patterns of redundancy and dispersion, they calculate the degree to which these metrics were different from the null expectation, given their species richness in a particular ecoregion. They concluded that focusing conservation efforts in areas with high species richness will maintain species richness and functional redundancy but not always the functional dispersion. They suggested that functional redundancy, as a means of insurance (i.e. when one species is able to replace a similar species from the same functional niche), and functional dispersion, as an indicator of response diversity, should be evaluated further as conservation objectives. In particular, they pointed to the need to provide a better assessment to functional dispersion since these might respond better to multiple threats, due to greater ecological recovery and stability.

In order to assess the vulnerability of all marine mammals to global warming under high and low greenhouse gas emission scenarios, Albouy et al. (2020), using a trait-based approach, developed a sensitivity index and combined it with exposure, defined as the magnitude of the changes in SST within the geographical range of each species, inferred

from global Earth system models future projections. Species sensitivity index to ocean warming (i.e. inability of the species to persist in its habitat) was based on an extensive review of the literature on fifteen traits categories (feeding, habitat, reproduction, social behavior and biology), traits that have been commonly used in CC vulnerability assessments (geographical range-related variable, diet specialization and habitat specialization, which reflect the plasticity of a species) and specific traits that are known to mediate the sensitivity of marine mammals to CC, such as traits related to habitat requirements (e.g. ice pack, as extrapolated from IUCN geographical range data (<http://iucnredlist.org>) and the Bio-ORACLE raster environmental spatial data (<https://www.bio-oracle.org/>). Sensitivity to warming was evaluated with a numerical scale (from the least to the most sensitive). e.g. the epipelagic modality of the 'habitat vertical specialization' trait was scored as most sensitive, as in the upper layers changes in temperature are high, while to the benthic and to mesopelagic modalities was assigned a lower score, and generalist got a 0 as score. The sum of all trait values resulted in an overall species-specific sensitivity ranking. The resulting values were then divided by the maximum sensitivity value obtained among species to set the sensitivity index between 0 (least sensitive species) and 1 (most sensitive species). Degree of exposure to ocean warming was computed by dividing the delta values of SST distribution into three parts. Each category was assigned a score from 0 to 2 from the lowest to the upper category, respectively. Species geographical range was divided into a grid of cells and the relative number (%) of cells occurring in each category provided exposure. A species was categorized as highly exposed to CC if it will face great temperature changes in a large proportion of its range.

Potential pitfalls of evaluating sensitivity and that should be taken into consideration, are due to the fact that physiological sensitivity varies among drivers (e.g. heat wave, hypoxia, ocean acidification) and species, and co-occurring drivers interact to buffer or enhance each other leading to both antagonistic and synergistic effects (Crain et al. 2008). Moreover, vulnerability can vary considerably among populations of the same species due to evolutionary processes (e.g. local adaptation or genetic drift, in Rilov et al. 2019).

3.2.1.5. Biological traits - data and data proxies

At present the availability of comprehensive trait data for numerous species is limited and systematic approaches that incorporate traits are absent (Lefcheck and Duffy 2015). These limitations may impede the adoption of such approaches among scientists and conservation managers. The challenge, and in some cases, the impossibility of directly measuring certain individual traits on preserved specimens may necessitate the use of published data opportunistically to assign scores to traits representing aspects such as reproductive behavior, lifespan, and feeding habits. However, inherent taxonomic biases

in fundamental biological information restrict the utilization of literature mining to well-studied species, such as many fish species and select macroinvertebrates. Therefore, a combination of new observations, expert opinions, and existing published data may yield robust information (Miatta et al. 2021).

The use of traits may offer some advantage over taxonomic species identification approaches as closely related species within the same family will be more similar to each other in terms of traits due to their shared evolutionary history, so that traits for related species can be inferred. However, it also present shortcomings such as: the choice of appropriate functional traits and their trade-offs with other traits given that a great diversity of traits are available, lack of consideration of intraspecific differences, databases are not always useful to species interactions, theoretical assumptions of trait-based studies are not always supported by experimental data etc. These shortcomings can be overcome by closer cooperation between empirical and theoretical researchers and by the development of standards for trait data collection (Zakharova et al, 2019 and literature therein). Recent efforts aim to enhance the accessibility and reliability of species trait data through curated and open-source databases like the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS), Lifewatch, EMODnet Biology project, the Coral Trait Database for corals (Madin et al. 2016) and sFDvent for hydrothermal vent species (Chapman et al. 2019), FishBase (www.fishbase.org/) and IUCN Red List of threatened Species (www.iucnredlist.org/), as to cite some examples. A more complete list of databases useful for biological traits extrapolated from D2.2 (WP2) is reported in this deliverable in the subparagraph 5.2.

3.2.2 Functional diversity

3.2.2.1 Functional diversity - definition

Functional diversity (i.e. the functional component of biodiversity) has been defined in Mouchet et al. (2010) as the diversity of functional traits that define the contribution of the organisms of a given species to different aspects of the functioning of the ecosystems where they occur (e.g., its dynamics, stability, productivity, nutrient balance, and other aspects).

The diversity of traits (functional diversity, i.e. feeding behavior, reproductive cycles etc) in a community reflects the ability of species to fill diverse niches, assimilate energy, and transfer it within and across ecosystems, and enhance and stabilize ecosystem processes (Lefcheck and Duffy 2015, Gagic, et al. 2015, Dee et al. 2016, Duffy et al. 2016).

3.2.2.2. Functional diversity - application to ABMTs prioritization, design and monitoring

Even small changes in the composition of a community whose species express specific functional traits, can affect the whole ecosystem processes and functioning. For example, changes can lead to alteration in resource utilization and food webs as well as the loss of keystone species (e.g. Hooper et al. 2002, Paine 2002). Functional diversity metrics are based on functional traits, i.e. characteristics of species that can be measured at individual level and are related to species growth, reproduction and survival. Measuring functional diversity therefore allows to generalize the functional contributions of species to ecosystems and contemplate the potential ecological consequences of their extinction whilst providing criteria for protection and conservation of important functions and ecosystem services. However, species diversity (which is often used as a surrogate of functional diversity measure) and functional diversity are not always correlated. For conservation perspectives, this stresses the need for assessing intra- and inter-habitat idiosyncrasies among functional and compositional nestedness and turnover of communities for a more comprehensive picture of possible protection scenarios. This is true especially for shallow coastal systems where diversity and spatial heterogeneity of marine habitats is high. Habitat-specific patterns of nestedness and turnover could indeed implicate different and conflicting conservation strategies (Bevilacqua and Terlizzi 2020). Functional diversity can be monitored to **measure resource use and predict changes in ecosystem processes** (Tilman 2001). Moreover, identifying functional traits differentiating species provide information on how **ecologically redundant or unique communities** are (Mouillot et al. 2014) and help predict their responses to climatic and human-based changes.

Functional diversity analysis has been applied and combined with other diversity metrics (species richness and phylogenetic diversity) for the **identification of priority areas where to improve conservation in relation to threats** (e.g. searching for worldwide hotspots for mammals and their spatial overlap with human threats, as described by Albouy et al. 2017). These authors measured functional diversity through the FRic (functional richness) index based on 14 animals' traits database. Maps showing the distribution of diversity metrics and its congruences with hotspots showed that the FRic index was weakly correlated with species richness, suggesting that the exclusive use of species richness as a benchmark for defining marine mammal biodiversity hotspots is not always reliable **to optimize site selection and spatial conservation strategies by providing scenarios**. Bevilacqua and Terlizzi (2020) provided a framework for combining information on compositional and functional β -diversity (referring to the heterogeneity in the distribution of biological entities from a taxonomic, phylogenetic and functional

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perspective, across space, time or any other gradient of variation components) to optimize sites (or habitats) selection for protection. This was done by analyzing dissimilarity patterns in species and functional trait composition in macrobenthic communities from the Mediterranean Sea and quantifying taxonomic and functional β -diversity among selected sites, evaluating turnover and nestedness, and comparing β -diversity patterns between assemblages occurring at different depths. They found that partitioning β -diversity components (functional and compositional ones) revealed a discrepancy, and the presence of functional hotspots, which would remain unnoticed when analyzing the overall compositional and functional β -diversity. They suggest that their findings could have profound implications for the optimization of conservation planning, stressing the need for assessing habitat-dependent idiosyncrasies in components of diversity. In their work they provide an example of information that can guide the prioritization of site/habitat protection (Figure 5 from Bevilacqua and Terlizzi 2020). Moreover they define conservation scenarios by partitioning β -diversity in the two components (nestedness and turnover) which are the basic mechanisms causing the overall variations in the identities of elements. These two components define diverse ecological processes driving biodiversity patterns. Nestedness relates to variations in the number of species (or functional traits, or any other type of items used to quantify diversity) due to gain or loss, so that the pools of species in less diverse assemblages appear nested as a strict subset of the more diverse ones; turnover occurs when species loss is balanced by the arrival of new ones. They also provide examples for combining information on compositional and functional β -diversity components to optimize sites (or habitats) selection for protection (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Conceptual framework for combining information on compositional and functional β -diversity components to optimize sites (or habitats) selection for protection. The example reports two sites or habitats (S1 and S2). Numbers in square boxes and diagrams indicate different species; same colors in boxes indicate the same or very similar functional traits. Van Venn diagrams represent the overlap between the functional space occupied by the communities in S1 and S2. In diagrams, shared species between S1 and S2 are reported in black and unique species are in red and blue, respectively (from Bevilacqua and Terlizzi, 2020): **case A**) when 50% of species on the total pool compositional β -diversity between the two communities is unshared ($\beta = 0.5$) both S1 and S2 should be selected to protect the whole regional pool of species; **case A1**) if β_{TURN} is the dominant component but functional turnover ($F\beta_{\text{TURN}}$) is not the dominant component of functional β -diversity ($F\beta$), selection of both sites will be necessary to protect all species and all functions; **case A2**) if functional nestedness ($F\beta_{\text{NES}}$) is dominant, selecting only S2 will be sufficient to protect most of the species and all functions. **case B**). If β is entirely (or mostly) due to compositional turnover (β_{TURN}), the selection of both S1 and S2 is supported. If, β is determined entirely by nestedness (β_{NES}), in order to protect all species is sufficient to select only S1; **case B1**) if β_{NES} is dominant, also $F\beta_{\text{NES}}$ is necessarily dominant (because if the species of a given community are a subset of another one, also their functional traits will be included in the functional space of the second community); **case B2**) if the degree of nestedness change, in both B1 and B2 selecting only the nesting site (S1) will ensure protection of all species and functions.

3.2.2.3. Functional diversity – methods

It is clear that in order to face the biodiversity crisis, conservation should prioritize those species that provide high functional diversity.

Measuring functional diversity (i.e. the functional component of biodiversity) is quantifying the distribution of functional units in a multidimensional space whose axes represent functional features (Mouchet et al. 2010, Villéger et al 2008). Functional diversity is usually studied through the analysis of functional traits, which represent biological, morphological, behavioral characteristics of target organisms (see this deliverable glossary for general traits term and previous subparagraph). Coleman et al. (2015) list some examples of functional traits of fish such as: total length (category body size), trophic level (category trophic Index), gregariousness (level of occurrence as solitary, couple, group of individuals) and diel (diurnal/nocturnal) activity pattern (category behavior), preferred substrate (hard, soft) and complexity preference (category habitat use), thermal affinity based on occupied temperature distribution (category physiology). Streit and Bellwood (2023) have clarified the way traits are used in research and their contribution to functionality. They identified two approaches with different research goals:

1. Community Cluster Traits primarily consider traits diversity in communities, the presence/absence of traits and, thus, a potential pool of available functions. They are useful to identify patterns in communities but unable to provide data on what these patterns mean and to translate diversity into ecological impacts.
2. Ecosystem Function Traits, by contrast, aim to quantify the realized intensity of specific functions. They are proxies for higher-order ecological processes, disregard diversity per se, but focus on causal linkages between traits and specific higher-order processes such as ecosystem functions and future ecological trajectories.

In this section, we consider methods that take into consideration community cluster traits.

A relevant protocol is the one developed by Palacio et al. (2022), which provides a series of steps for the systematic and reproducible design and development of trait-based studies or assessments (Fig. 6):

- Conceptualization and explicit definition of an ecological question, generally based on a hypothesis-driven framework (Step 1)
- Follow a well-defined ecological rationale to inform appropriate sampling or experimental designs (Step 2)
- Collection of occurrence data (Step 3)
- Collection of species trait data, which is the essential information for any trait analysis (Step 4)

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- Data exploration (Step 5)
- Core analysis with functional traits (Step 6)
- Validation, interpretation and reporting of results (Step 7)
- Data and code sharing to ensure the reproducibility of the entire pipeline (Step 8).

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Figure 6. Protocol for the design and development of functional diversity trait-based studies and assessments (from Palacio et al. 2022).

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3.2.2.4. Functional diversity - metrics and indexes

Functional diversity includes metrics such as functional groups, functional richness; functional divergence; functional evenness; functional redundancy (see also Mason et al. 2005). Functional groups are based on traits such as form, size, life-history, feeding and behavior. As an example Barbera et al (2012) used the following traits to describe functional diversity in the epifaunal communities of Menorca: feeding habits (deposit feeder, filter/suspension feeder, scavenger/opportunist, predator, grazer); habit and behavior (sessile, vagile-swimmer-high-medium mobility, crawl-low mobility), burrow; life history (Individual, colonial); body form (flat, mound-roundness, erect, uncrustant, vermiform-tube), body size (small/medium/large).

Traditional functional diversity indices include metrics based on the sum or average of functional distances between species pairs in multivariate functional trait space, the distances between species along hierarchical classification or the distribution of abundance along functional trait axes (see Miatta et al 2021 and literature therein).

Community-scale rarity and functional structure metrics have been used as proxies of functional redundancy and functional specialization.

Metrics and indexes related to functional diversity have been proposed by Mouillot et al. (2013), and then widely applied in studies about functional diversity. The definitions of the functional diversity indices are reported in box 1.

Box 1. Definition of functional diversity indexes and related metrics (from Mouillot et al., 2013)

- *Functional dissimilarity*: the dissimilarity in the functional space occupied by two communities.
- *Functional divergence*: the proportion of total abundance supported by species with the most extreme trait values within a community.
- *Functional diversity*: the distribution of species and their abundances in the functional space of a given community.
- *Functional evenness*: the regularity of the distribution and relative abundance of species in functional space for a given community.
- *Functional identity*: the mean value of functional traits, weighted by abundance, across all species present in a given community.
- *Functional originality*: the isolation of a species in the functional space occupied by a given community.
- *Functional richness*: the volume of multidimensional space occupied by all species in a community within functional space.
- *Functional specialization*: the mean distance of a species from the rest of the species pool in functional space.

FD index are traditionally based on a functional dendrogram and in certain cases may lead to a biased assessment of functional diversity and inaccurate ecological conclusions (Maire et al. 2015). On the other hand, the functional richness index (FRic; Villéger et al. 2008) which considers the volume of the functional space occupied by species through the calculation convex hull volumes and that encompasses the entire trait space filled by all species in an assemblage is considered a more reliable approach by some authors (Villéger et al. 2008, Albouy et al. 2020).

Mammola and Cardoso (2020) provided a clear framework to assess different component of FD including alpha and beta diversity, dispersion, evenness, contribution and originality, within a multidimensional setting (Fig 7).

Figure 7. Possible representations of functional diversity (FD) based on two hypothetical traits and two communities, represented in turquoise and orange, respectively (a) a trait-based distance matrix among species (trait space) is represented by a functional dendrogram, the functional richness = total branch length of a tree linking all species in the community; (b) trait space is represented by the minimum convex hull comprising the species occupying the trait space. the functional richness = area of the convex hull; (c) the trait space can be constructed using kernel density hypervolumes, approximated as a cloud of stochastic points sampled based for example on a set of traits of the species in the community functional richness = volume of the hypervolume delineated by the stochastic points (from Mammola and Cardoso 2020).

Bevilacqua and Terlizzi (2020) suggested the calculation of functional turnover and nestedness (β -diversity) to assess the replacements or loss of functional traits/groups across assemblages in space.

3.2.2.5 Functional diversity - data and proxies

In studies about functional diversity from a perspective of cluster community traits (i.e., to understand patterns of functional diversity, *sensu* Streit and Bellwood, 2023) functional traits are usually collected in many ways. For instance, traits values are mined from scientific literature searching the mainstream web tools (i.e., Web of Science, Scopus, Google Scholar), retrieved from eminent online catalogs and databases, e.g., 'FishBase' (www.fishbase.org/), 'SeaLifeBase' (www.sealifebase.org). AlgaeBase (<https://www.algaebase.org/>). Community science datasets (Callaghan et al. 2021) and museum/herbarium collections (Perez et al., 2020) can also be used to collect traits. Data availability about traits is a limiting factor, since trait values may not be available for the

species targeted in a study. Trait selection and discard is an essential methodological step that needs proper reflection and justification (Palacio et al., 2022).

Although Condachou et al (2023) recently suggested that, despite taxonomic uncertainties, even the eDNA approach can become a powerful tool to estimate reliable functional diversity values, completely inferring functional diversity from phylogenetic and taxonomic diversity is in many times not appropriate. Functional diversity based on biological traits can complement taxonomic approaches, but taxonomic diversity is not always a proxy for evaluating ecosystem functioning which is more dependent on functional traits rather than species richness (Wong et al. 2015). Mazel et al. (2018) tested the hypothesis that species traits often reflect shared evolutionary history and that maximizing phylogenetic diversity should indirectly capture the functional one, and concluded that this could be a risk in conservation strategy.

3.2.3 Trophic ecology

3.2.3.1 Trophic ecology - definition

Trophic ecology investigates how various organisms at different feeding (trophic) levels interact within an ecosystem. In general, feeding or trophic relationships are represented as a food web or as a food chain.

3.2.3.2 Trophic ecology - application to ABMTs prioritization, design and monitoring

Food webs are central entities mediating major processes as well as pressures in marine ecosystems, providing a functional link between individuals and populations, ecosystem functioning and resilience, and ultimately, ecosystem services (Eero et al. 2021). To design effective conservation strategies, aspects such as trophic ecology should be considered since main prey items or key feeding grounds are essential for species and community stability and functioning. Therefore, in order to boost species conservation (particularly for top predators) it is advisable to carefully consider the resources which sustain populations and to identify key feeding grounds. This requires a broader understanding of foraging ecology, main prey, trophic position, and intra-population patterns in the diet (Heupel et al., 2014, Simpfendorfer et al., 2011).

Trophic interactions are indeed an important aspect of (a) **ecosystem stability**, for example they have been used to model community interactions and predict **alternative stable states of these for reserve design** (Baskett et al. 2011). These interactions are usually complex to be measured, and it is difficult to predict how one species will respond to higher (or lower) numbers of other species. For example, the increase of one predator

abundance might decrease the abundance of some preferable preys, but not affect others secondary preys preferentially consumed by other predators. To gain a better understanding of the interactions among all parts of an ecosystem, we must ideally develop a food web linking all groups from primary producers like phytoplankton and algae, to grazers to predators.

Trophic niche, stable isotopes and predator biomass data have highlighted the benefits obtained from the use of large offshore MPAs as a tool for ecosystem restoration from trawling impact in two fishery reserves off the northern Sicily coast (Mediterranean Sea) (Agnetta et al. 2019). Notwithstanding this, the benefits of protection are not always immediate for top predators as weakened trophic cascades linked to fishing (trawling) restrictions can occur. This can be for instance because of: large size preys escape predation (Mumby et al. 2006), shifts of preys for predators (Kellner et al. 2010), intraspecific competition that might reduce the size of predators and their feeding rates on prey (Guidetti 2006), and random movements of predators and preys across protected and unprotected areas (Jiao et al. 2016). Despite these limitations, trophic ecology criteria are useful indicators to be integrated with other criteria (b) **to monitor the effectiveness of ABMTs and to develop scenarios for their adaptive management (e.g. reserve effect)**. The impact of size prey refugia on the expectation of species responses to reserve establishment is an important dynamic to consider when designing and monitoring marine reserves (Baskett 2006). However, as highlighted for trophic cascades after reserve establishment, incorporating size prey refugia could lead to unexpected expectations as decreases in the harvest rate threshold of piscivores (predators) to depletion. This increase in piscivore vulnerability to fishing with prey size refugia is due to smaller piscivore production because of less prey available. The theoretical potential for size refugia to prevent trophic cascades generalizes the empirical results obtained by Mumby et al. (2006) who suggested that trophic cascades after reserve establishment are unlikely in systems where herbivores are harvested and have a size refugia from predation. The effect of overfishing, by reducing predators and weakening their trophic role, may propagate down in food webs and drive alternating patterns of abundance at consecutively lower trophic levels (two or more trophic links below the exploited predator). This effect, called Fishery-Induced trophic cascades (FITC), can alter marine ecosystems. Therefore, c) the **identification of vulnerable ecosystems and processes** within a risk-assessment framework to forecast FITC is extremely important for management and conservation prioritization. As an example, understanding the structural properties of food webs may indicate key species (Fig. 4 in Gaichas and Francis 2008) and strong interactions (Bascompte et al. 2005) with the highest risk for cascading effects. Identifying ecosystem features that confer resilience to exploitation will also help indicate high-risk ecosystems. However, information is not easily available since information on food-web dynamics is lacking for most exploited systems and to date there has been little

emphasis on forecasting FITCs and the thresholds of consumer exploitation that may trigger them (Salomon et al., 2010). In fact, although fishing clearly can induce change in marine food webs, the causes of major community shifts are often complex and involve more than just top-down control. Multiple stressors and the possibility of synergistic effects can complicate the prediction of FITCs and management of their drivers. Phase shifts, for example, may be triggered by reduction in stock due to fishing, making populations strongly dependent on annual recruitment and thus more vulnerable to environmental fluctuations, such as changes of climate (Salomon et al. 2010).

Additionally the exchange of energy between adjacent ecosystems, initially conceptualized for saltmarshes as the “outwelling” hypothesis (*sensu* Odum et al. 1979), it is now recognized to be a widespread process potentially impacting biogeochemical cycles and enhancing biological production and fisheries yields in coastal seas. It has emphasized that effective management and protection measures can be achieved only through a cross-seascapes approach and a deep understanding of the synergic processes driving biodiversity and functioning in neighboring environments. Understanding the level on which marine coastal communities and food webs are dependent on terrestrial/estuarine trophic resources is extremely important in areas that are predicted to be impacted by climate and other anthropogenic changes (McKee et al. 2004, Hyndes et al. 2014, Bongiorno et al. 2018 and literature therein).

Trophic ecology can thus provide a picture of the level of trophic connectivity (food supply of one area to another, see also the section connectivity) which can be another important criterion for the designation of networks of protected areas.

3.2.3.3 Trophic ecology - methods

Currently, understanding the environmental status of food webs remains challenging task since evaluations are limited by data on key ecosystem elements, by the availability of indicators that incorporate relevant guilds and by the difficulty in establishing cause-effect relations between pressures and health status, as multiple overlapping pressures can affect taxonomic elements differently (Machado et al. 2021). Various human-induced pressures, including overexploitation, pollution, eutrophication, invasive species and CC can impact the structure and dynamics of food webs, by altering the balance between organisms (Ullah et al. 2018). These threats can operate at different spatial scales and exert diverse bottom-up or top-down effects on food webs. Identifying and monitoring these processes is challenging, making it difficult to set effective management objectives and provide scientific guidance on achieving them (Rombouts et al. 2013a). Methods to study trophic ecology include stable isotope and stomach content analyses and modeling food webs tools.

Most of our current understanding of trophic ecology and interactions of fish populations comes from dietary studies based on the analysis of stomach contents, providing important information about many facets of the biology and ecology of fishes and aquatic ecosystems (Braga et al. 2012, Manko 2016), although for migratory species such as sharks, that use wide range of habitats for feeding, there is need to describe diet using a more integrative approach. The methods that are used for stomach-content analysis of fish comprise three main approaches (Amundsen and Sánchez-Hernández. 2019): presence-absence, numerical and bulk, the latter including the gravimetric, mass reconstruction, volumetric, point and relative-fullness methods (Hyslop 1980).

Stable isotopes can provide a time-integrated depiction of consumer diet and trophic relationships (Vander Zanden et al. 2015). This can be matched with Bayesian mixing models, which estimate probability distributions of source contributions, and contribute to defining consumer diet (Phillips et al. 2014). Moreover, matching of stable isotope analysis and mixing models with qualitative quantitative studies of communities has been recently addressed as an effective strategy to assess and disentangle the effects of multiple environmental impacts in coastal marine ecosystems (Mancinelli and Vizzini 2014). Despite the fact that many stable isotope field studies assume that the isotopic composition of animal tissues is in equilibrium with diet, this is not the case in many situations, and can lead to highly misleading food web interpretations. Diet-tissue discrimination and its variability are now reasonably well-characterized, and studies routinely incorporate the observed variability in diet-tissue discrimination into mixing model outputs (Kadye et al. 2020). Instead, synthetic knowledge is still missing about isotopic turnover and half-life in animal tissues. Consideration of the time scale of isotopic incorporation in animal tissues can be important in the interpretation of stable isotope results (Vander Zanden et al. 2015). More recently, DNA-based dietary analysis has also been adopted (Jakubavičiūtė et al. 2017, Kress et al. 2015, Valentini et al. 2009). The easiest way to assess the dietary composition of a fish population is to record the presence or absence of each prey taxon across all sampled individuals and express their frequency of occurrence in the stomachs as an indicator of prey importance. Fish stomach content has been investigated to see how this could contribute to the definition of EBSAs (e.g. Mc Quinn et al. 2012, King et al. 2013).

Trophic modeling tools are used to describe energy flow between the different species or trophic groups in an ecosystem and can help to better understand and predict ecosystem-level effects of marine resource management and investigate different conservation strategies. Models can be developed linking each group through its abundance and the proportion of species in other trophic groups that are consumed. They should include low trophic level (basic resources) i.e. usually primary producers (algae, phytoplankton and seagrasses). The organic matter (dead and alive primary food sources) is transferred to

higher trophic levels when the primary producers are consumed or grazed by consumers (higher trophic levels). The model thus can predict how each trophic group will be affected if the abundance of one or many species changes. Mass-balance models bring together varied field data and literature information to provide a self-consistent picture of the trophic structure of a given ecosystem. Since parameters are not always known, inverse methods have been adopted to reconstruct flux through an ecosystem, by using field and literature data with a certain uncertainty. Ecopath with EcoSim (EwE) software is a used approach to this problem (e.g. Mendoza 1993, Wolff 1994, Jarre-Teichmann et al. 1998, Arreguin-Sanchez et al. 2002, Jiang and Gibbs 2005). Parameters such as biomass and diet fractions are numerically adjusted with specific mathematical tools (e.g Ecoranger, within Ecopath/EcoSim) or others, to achieve a plausible balanced model, and allow the effects of parameter uncertainty (Pinkerton et al. 2007).

Finally, Dekker et al. (2017) developed a spatially explicit systematic conservation planning using MARXAN and incorporated trophic level information of fish (species feeding traits). They used the trophic level of each species obtained from FishBase (herbivores, detritivores, and carnivores) and on the basis of this divided into prey and predators. Results showed that this approach while simultaneously identifying areas that represent a more diverse species pool and enhancing the identification of priority refugia for prey species in the lower position of the trophic web, led to a different spatial configuration of priority areas at no additional cost (more efficient plan). This approach was tested in a riverine environment but can be applicable to other realms.

3.2.3.4 Trophic ecology - metrics and indexes

In our literature, the criteria-keywords for ABMTs prioritization, design and management often reported were: food web length, structure and/or complexity; feeding modes (trophic structure) and energy flow from models, abundance prey/predator, weight of trophic groups, and stable isotopes, biomass used to predict predator, trophic levels, productivity.

Food webs are also analyzed in terms of structural and functional traits including trophic levels, transfer efficiency, trophic role of species and keystone-ness, trophic spectra and other synthetic ecological indicator, these have been analyzed in Lercari and Francisco (2009), and Libralato et al. (2010).

With the onset of the MSFD, the development of food web assessment indicators has evolved significantly. Descriptor 4 (D4 Food Webs) requires the assessment of trophic guilds of an ecosystem and includes two primary Criteria (D4C1 and D4C2) and two secondary Criteria (D4C3 and D4C4). D4C1 correspond to "the diversity (species composition and their relative abundance) of the trophic guild is not adversely affected due to anthropogenic pressures", D4C2 "the balance of total abundance between the

trophic guilds is not adversely affected due to anthropogenic pressures”, D4C3 “the size distribution of individuals across the trophic guild is not adversely affected due to anthropogenic pressures”, D4C4 “productivity of the trophic guild is not adversely affected due to anthropogenic pressures”.

To date, a variety of food web indicators exist but many remain conceptual. However, Tam et al. (2017) identified a selection of operational food-web indicators for the assessment in marine waters: the primary production required to sustain a fishery, the productivity of seabirds (or charismatic megafauna), zooplankton indicators, primary productivity, integrated trophic indicators and the biomass of trophic guilds. As an example of application, in the OSPAR Quality Status Reports 2023, the production of phytoplankton as well as changes in their consumers (zooplankton) were assessed at the North-East Atlantic scale (OSPAR 2023). Despite an increasing use of food web indicators to assess Good Environmental Status by European Member States, one of the challenges remain the setting of thresholds for D4 Criteria at the regional and sub-regional scale (Vasilakopoulos et al. 2022) and more efforts are needed to develop threshold-based reference points (Tam et al. 2017). Modeling tools in combination with empirical analyses could further improve the development of operational indicators for ecosystem-based management in general (de Jonge, 2007, Rombouts et al. 2013b, Korpinen et al. 2022).

3.2.3.5 Trophic ecology - data and data proxies

Relevant data for trophic ecology are biomass populations of different trophic levels as well as parameters like primary and secondary production rates, assimilation, respiration and mortality rates, grazing and predatory rates, diet composition etc. Community data such as diversity, species composition, abundance, biomass, and distribution also provide relevant information for trophic ecology. Individual properties such as size are also relevant. Size is an important parameter and may be used to extrapolate from individuals to community, metrics such as secondary production (Kimmel 2019, and references therein), as well as the occurrence and strength of feeding interactions (Woodward et al. 2005).

Moreover, understanding diets can indicate which species are strongly interacting and what may happen if important predators or prey numbers change dramatically. Diet data help to understand competitive and predator-prey dynamics and contribute to ecosystem models to support management decisions. diet data together with catch data help in understanding the effects of fishery management actions, habitat shifts, and CC.

Data from the most common methodological tracing methods are derived by visual analysis (stomach, gut or feces content analyses), DNA-based (DNA of stomach, gut or

feces content analyses), biomarkers (fatty acid analyses), stable isotopes ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ analyses) compounds specific stable isotopes ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ amino acid analyses, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ fatty acid analyses). A review has been provided by Nielsen et al. (2017).

Data availability remains an issue for trophic ecology. However, to support modeling applications and assessments, online diet databases of marine taxa are available (e.g. Fishbase, SeaLifeBase, DAPSTOM, Food Habits Database, MesopTroph). Some databases on trophic markers are also available (e.g., MarTurtSI, SCAR). Despite that, undoubtedly, large volumes of relevant data remain scattered in the literature or unpublished, making it difficult and laborious to find and reuse the data.

3.2.4.1 Connectivity - definition:

Ecological connectivity is defined by UNEP (2019) as “the degree to which landscapes and seascapes allow species to move freely and ecological processes to function unimpeded”. This concept derived from the fact that most living organisms (populations, and that of individuals, genes, gametes, and propagules) are largely dependent on more than one habitat, and might need to freely move (e.g. either passively transported by currents or actively migrate) among communities, and ecosystems, to accomplish their vital functions (e.g. feeding and breeding) and as such can be a major determinant of marine community structure and ecosystem functioning (Hilty et al. 2020).

Connectivity can be classified according to different ecological level:

Demographic or population connectivity: consist in the movement of individuals among neighboring local populations, this influences the size (i.e., number of individuals) and structure (i.e. sizes, ages, and sexes of individuals) of each subpopulation. These characteristics can, in turn, influence critical demographic rates (e.g. births, deaths, immigration, and emigration) and vulnerability of the overall population to impacts and extinction. Therefore, the existence of a metapopulation (population connected by individuals' movements) greatly influences population resilience (ability to recover from a perturbation), extinction, persistence. Local populations that produce lots of gametes or larvae can act as 'sources', exporting individuals to replenish less persistent and productive 'sink' populations, and this can be an important feature to consider for the design of ABMTs and networks.

Genetic connectivity: based on the exchange of genetic materials (gene) through gametes, propagules, and adult movements. It can be important for the spatial patterns of the genetic diversity within populations, and it is critical to the ability of species to adapt to changing environmental conditions. Indeed, the more genetically similar the population of a species is, the higher is their capacity for gene exchange. The degree to which

populations differ genetically from one another with increasing distance “isolation by distance” is one method used to estimate how far individuals, especially larvae, travel (Kinlan and Gaines 2003, Palumbi 2003). In case of anthropogenic impacts affecting species performance, PAs measures can serve as refuge from anthropogenic selection of genetics (Barnett and Baskett 2015). However, a single MPA might only protect a portion of a species' genetic diversity, and in this case a network of MPAs can protect a wider spectrum of genetic diversity of a species across its dispersion area.

Community connectivity: it consists in the movement of multiple species among distinct ecological communities, i.e, the collection of species that co-occur and interact with one another in a particular habitat. Because species differ in the distance that individuals move (e.g. spores of algae and larvae of corals move much shorter distances than larvae of fishes), the size and spacing of MPAs especially those intended to conserve entire ecosystems need to accommodate these differences to protect the communities they are intended to protect, and will affect the goals of protecting biogenic habitat that acts as nursery grounds, etc.

Ecosystem connectivity: it can be defined as the results from the movement of multiple species among distinct ecological communities, along with the movement of chemicals (e.g., nutrients and pollutants), energy (in the form of organisms), and materials (e.g. sediments and debris). Connectivity can have a strong impact on ecosystems that receive nutrients or species, enhancing their productivity or resilience also called “ecosystem subsidies”. Some examples are the influx of phytoplankton or zooplankton from offshore to nearshore ecosystems, as source of food for many predators, invertebrates and fishes, which in turn, are consumed by other species, fuelling a plankton-based food web or as in the case of nutrients, organic matter originated from river systems that are supplied to nearby estuarine and coastal marine systems, influencing their composition in species and productivity and fuels detritus-based food webs in recipient ecosystems that otherwise would lack source of plant production (references in Carr et al, 2017, Bongiorno et al. 2018 and literature therein). Ecosystem connectivity also entails the movement of mobile species which use different habitats during their life cycle. For example, ensuring connectivity between nursery and other important areas (foraging, reproduction) in a network of MPAs contributes to the structure, functions productivity and thus services the ecosystem can provide, apart from influencing ecosystem resilience in the face of CC impacts. Examples are reported in Carr et al (2017): in the Great Barrier Reef, where corals have been overgrown by macroalgae because of the decrease of algal grazing or physical damage of corals, the existence of adjacent seagrass and mangrove ecosystems might serve as nurseries for herbivorous fish and foster coral recovery (Adam et al., 2011; Olds et al 2012a,b). It should be considered also that ecosystem connectivity can be also detrimental, in the case the movements of species, materials create inhospitable

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conditions that can affect ecosystem structure and functions, diminishing productivity (for example hypoxia caused by terrestrial runoff can be lethal to organisms such as the juveniles of offshore fishes that use estuaries as nursery habitats).

3.2.4.2. Connectivity - application to ABMTs prioritization, design and management

In order to efficiently move toward the next target of global marine conservation (30% by 2030) there is an urgent need to efficiently conserve, manage and restore biodiversity and functioning of natural systems throughout connectivity (Hilty et al. 2020; Balbar and Mataxas 2019). The need to include connectivity vs other criteria in conservation and management depends on the purpose of the MPA, on factors such as whether the MPA is species-, community-, or ecosystem-focused and on the environmental and ecological characteristics of the target species, communities, or ecosystems. In this direction, several factors should be taken into account, including: the location of an MPA; the size and shape of an MPA; whether the MPA is an individual, stand-alone site or is part of a set of inter-dependent MPAs (i.e., a network of MPAs); whether the species, communities, and/or ecosystems of concern are located inside or outside MPA boundaries; and, the operative management regimes in the areas around an MPA.

These principles can be divided on the basis of those seeking to:

1. to restore or maintain species
2. to restore or maintain ecological communities and ecosystems.

For the first ones at the level of a species, traits to be considered are: duration of larval phase, adult mobility etc. Conditions that pose the requirement of considering connectivity could span from species that occupy isolated habitats and have long pelagic larval durations in deeper sea areas with strong directional currents to species with short pelagic durations that occupy fragmented habitats in shallow topographically complex sea areas with weak and variable currents (Virtanen et al. 2019). The second ones related to ecological communities and ecosystems are summarized in Table 1 and 2 (obtained from Supplementary table S1 and S2, Carr et al. 2017).

Table 1: Summary of principles for incorporating ecological spatial connectivity into the design and management of networks of MPAs created for the purpose of protecting particular species (from Tables S1, S2 in Carr et al. 2017).

<i>Species Characteristics</i>	<i>Conservation Goal</i>	<i>Conservation Action</i>	<i>MPA Design, Use, and Management Principles</i>
Short distance dispersers	Restore or maintain populations WITHIN the boundaries of MPA	Consider a standalone MPA	<i>The larger the MPA and higher the habitat quality, the more likely populations within the MPA will be self-sustaining within that individual MPA.</i>
			<i>MPA size should be scaled to match the home range of adults (the area an adult individual inhabits over its lifetime) to ensure that adults remain and are protected within that MPA.</i>
			<i>For species whose adults migrate among adjacent ecosystems (e.g., across depth gradients), siting and sizing MPAs to include multiple ecosystems increases the protection and access to those ecosystems.</i>
Long distance dispersers	Restore or maintain populations within the boundaries of MPA	Consider a network of MPAs	<i>Create and manage MPA networks that facilitate recruitment within and among PAs.</i>
		Consider an MPA in area of well-managed fisheries	<i>Create an MPA and manage fisheries in the areas outside the MPA to ensure that the adult fish populations outside the MPA are sufficiently robust to contribute larvae to the MPA.</i>
	Restore or maintain populations outside the boundaries of MPA -- by contributing larvae to populations outside of MPA	Consider multiple smaller MPAs	<i>For MPAs to contribute to target populations outside their boundaries, many smaller MPAs may be more effective than single large MPAs of the same area (or proportion of a regional population).</i> <i>MPAs should include high quality, productive adult habitat and species need to be well protected.</i> <i>The location of an MPA in a pattern of ocean circulation will determine whether and to which populations larvae are delivered.</i>
Any mobile species	Restore or maintain populations outside the boundaries of	Consider MPAs that contain nursery habitat	<i>The MPAs should be located in close proximity to adult populations outside their boundaries.</i>
			<i>The MPAs should be located on productive nursery grounds.</i>

	MPA -- by contributing Juveniles to populations outside of MPA		<i>MPA management needs to protect the quality of that natural nursery habitat by protecting the biotic (e.g., seagrasses, mangroves) and abiotic (e.g., water quality, seafloor features) conditions required for the growth and survival of juveniles.</i>
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Table 2: Summary of principles for incorporating ecological spatial connectivity into the design and management of networks of MPAs created for the purpose of protecting ecological communities and ecosystems.

Conservation Goal	Conservation Action	MPA Design, Use, and Management Principles
Protecting the structure, functions and services of ecological communities and ecosystems	Consider a network of MPAs	<i>Connectivity between protected communities and ecosystems requires that MPAs near one another include similar habitats and ecosystems.</i>
		<i>MPAs should be spaced within the dispersal distances of the key species that constitute and shape the communities</i>
		<i>MPA size and spacing are inter-related. MPAs need to be spaced close enough for long and intermediate dispersing species to disperse between MPAs with similar ecosystems.</i>
		<i>Larger, more self-replenishing MPAs can be spaced further apart, whereas smaller MPAs should be spaced closer together to enhance connectivity</i>
		<i>MPAs that include multiple habitat types and associated communities and ecosystems are more likely to protect the natural structure and function of each of those communities and ecosystems by ensuring connectivity</i>
		<i>MPAs that extend across a range of water depths and include multiple substratum types are likely to include a diversity of communities and ecosystems and facilitate interaction among those communities and ecosystems.</i>
		<i>Protecting the diversity of species, structures and functions of a specific community or ecosystem type and the resources and services it supports requires that MPA networks protect that ecosystem or community type across a broad geographic gradient.</i>
		<i>Adjacent ecosystems, including those on land, need to be managed such that deleterious impacts to ecosystems within an MPA are prevented.</i>

Connectivity might become essential mainly when:

- a single ABMT is characterized by limited self-recruitment or when the size of the proposed area is not large, enough for the population to be self-seeding and thus necessary to ***maintain viable populations*** (Marti-Puig et al., 2013). In this case knowledge on connectivity will support the reshaping/ enlargement of MPAs to provide self-seeding sources/supply.
- species/population rely on different habitats for their life cycle or are characterized by low local retention; in that case a good level of connectivity will ***maintain population community persistence***, or when a *network of ecologically coherent and connected MPAs* and other effective conservation measures should be designed to preserve highly mobile or fragmented species (Hilty et al. 2020).

ABMTs networks is the establishment and maximization of connectivity links between individual MPAs (Woodley et al. 2012), through dispersal of eggs, larvae, juveniles and/or adults (Magris et al. 2018). In case of fragmented populations, connectivity should help to identify areas adjacent or contiguous habitats and distance to protect foraging movements and ontogenetic migrations for different life cycle stages. A network based on connectivity should help in protecting species genetic diversity, as a source of healthy spawning stocks and for creating stepping-stones or corridors between existing or new designated areas (Grüss et al. 2011, D'Aloia et al. 2017).

Ensuring connectivity through networking, should be the means to achieve demographic persistence particularly in the face of CC (Magris et al. 2014). Indeed, connectivity-informed ABMTs and networks might address the effects of CC on the marine environment, focusing on changes in marine species' distributions, abundances, and productivities, and the cascading effects these species-level changes produce in ecological communities and ecosystems.

Sources and destinations of larvae or propagules can be identified as separate spatial layers and considered in full-scale spatial prioritization, because involving data on population connectivity is an important determinant of meta-population persistence. An example of flow of questions that might help to understand if connectivity should be prioritized are:

- Is the habitat large enough for the population to be self-seeding?
- Are propagules from adjacent subpopulations needed for local population maintenance?
- What is the role played by the protected sub-populations with respect to the resilience of meta-population? (e.g., in Rozenfeld et al. 2008; Watson et al. 2011)

3.2.4.3. Connectivity - methods

Main methods to measure connectivity are: modelling, animal tagging, genetics (to study gene flow linked to reproduction), simple observation, seascape measures (e.g., habitat linkages) using tools such as Marxan (Bryan-Brown et al. 2017; Balbar and Metaxas, 2019). Depending on the method used to collect connectivity data, various metrics can be used to elucidate connectivity patterns.

Modelling approaches: Individual-based modelling approaches yielding dispersal trajectories, connectivity matrices (i.e., source distribution matrix, for example obtained through electronic or natural passive tagging methods) and dispersal kernels are commonly used. Some authors have tailored metrics to taxa with different spawning and larval traits and have further combined them in a multi-species approach. Other metrics involve local retention/population persistence in MPA using fecundity or survival data; however, those data are complex and not always available (Burgess et al. 2012). Larval dispersal models allow considering wide spatial and temporal scales, as well as multiple taxa, and have shown a good correlation with empirical connectivity estimates. Dispersal simulations need data about marine currents transporting larvae at sea. These data usually come from hydrodynamic simulations that possibly should provide a reliable and validated representation of both magnitude and direction of marine currents. Moreover, the high-variability of the same currents should be considered at spatio-temporal scales relevant for both dispersal processes (larval scale) and regional connectivity estimates (population scale, including demographic variability). Recent studies have shown that to obtain reliable connectivity estimates one has to consider hydrodynamic simulations that are validated against available observations and at a spatial resolution that is sufficient to resolve the dynamics important for connectivity (such as coastal dynamic, eddies, i.e., order of a few hundreds of meters, Saint-Amandi et al. 2023). It was also shown that, at least for the North-Western Mediterranean, horizontal resolution was the most influential factor on simulated connectivity patterns (Sciascia et al. 2022).

In dispersal simulations, propagules (e.g., spores, seeds, rafts, eggs and larvae) are assumed to either drift passively with ocean currents or have simple behavior (e.g., sinking, diel vertical migration). Although this behavior might not precisely reflect small scale movements, it allows detecting connectivity patterns at broader scales (Assis et al., 2018; Shanks et al., 2003). These models incorporate also other empirical biological components (e.g., planktonic propagule duration, a proxy of dispersal distances that can last from few hours to hundreds of days see Faurby and Barber, 2012).

Genetic methods: these methods have been used in the management plans of only a few MPAs as data is more difficult to obtain because it is more expensive and time consuming.

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However, when available they can provide interesting information such as the genetic structure and diversity of metapopulations on scales of 1–100km (Beltrán et al. 2017). Inclusion of phylogenetic diversity, intraspecific genetic diversity and taxonomic diversity can increase the comprehensiveness of systems of marine conservation areas; this latter can benefit from the rapid generation of information provided by eDNA techniques. The integration of connectivity and adaptive genetic diversity can help create networks of MPAs because they ensure greater long-term persistence of biodiversity (Andrello et al. 2023 and literature therein). Metrics obtained through genetics are: genetic diversity, or connectivity matrices to calculate network metrics such as betweenness centrality.

New tools are becoming accessible to managers to include connectivity in. The R toolbox 'best MPA' aims to explore alternative MPA network designs and assess trade-offs of different ecological decisions. Marxan also allows for connectivity to be incorporated as a discrete feature and Zonation is another spatial planning tool, to optimise for connections through corridors or apply penalties based on boundary lengths. A newly developed tool, MarxanConnect, provides a graphical user interface to incorporate connectivity matrices and landscape connectivity data into Marxan. Simpler tools, such as a decision tree, can allow managers to incorporate size and spacing into MPA planning, if data on connectivity are limited (Balbar and Metaxas, 2019 and literature therein).

3.2.4.4 Connectivity - metrics and indexes

Genetic diversity, or connectivity matrices to calculate network metrics such as betweenness centrality can be calculated by genetic methods centrality). Metrics can also be calculated from proximity of habitats (Euclidean distance) or inferring source populations based on circulation patterns and residence times. Metrics such as local retention, betweenness centrality and outflow are particularly useful to incorporate in MPA design (Burgess et al., 2014; Magris et al., 2018). Local retention, the proportion of reproductive output that recruits back in the donor population, provides details on replacement and therefore persistence of a population. However, Burgess et al. (2014) identified that self-persistence, the proportion of total recruitment to a population that was produced by the population itself, is often used instead, although it provides no information on persistence. Keeley et al (2021) described several metrics to calculate the connectivity of single MPAs or networks for land- and sea-scapes, and monitor changes over time. These metrics fall into four categories: structural connectivity metrics derived from binary maps and species-nonspecific spatial functions, connectivity metrics derived from binary maps and species-specific population sizes and dispersal functions; metrics derived from multi-state maps and species responses to those states, and metrics of

functional connectivity reflecting observed flow of organisms or genes. Data on structural connectivity are not always available, as dedicated databases are not complete, lack of data is even worse for functional connectivity metrics, but estimating these metrics is becoming more feasible as movement data becomes easier to obtain and as our ability to infer species-specific resistance from such data improves. Perhaps the biggest improvement in functional connectivity will come from reduced cost and improved resolution of metrics related to gene flow (Keeley et al. 2021 and literature therein). These authors provided examples of metrics (and data needed) that can be used depending on ABMTs conservation/management goals.

Structural connectivity metrics (reflect the physical arrangement of habitat within the surrounding nonhabitat (matrix):

- distance to nearest neighbor patch (data: patch boundaries, distance between focal patches),
- distance to nearest occupied patch (data: patch boundaries, distance between focal patches, occupancy status of patch),
- degree of Connectedness, fraction of nodes connected to a focal node. (low-degree patches are vulnerable to extinction if neighboring patches are lost. High-degree patches may be sources or sinks, depending on patch size and quality, data: total number of habitat patches, euclidean distances between patches), etc.

Functional connectivity metrics (degree to which an ecoscape -including the matrix between patches of habitat – facilitates or impedes the movement of focal organisms:

- measurements of gene flow (data: analysis of genetic material from the connected patches can support qualitative inferences about whether gene flow has occurred. By comparing the genetic similarity between connected patches to that of isolated patches and to two locations in a large patch gene flow can be quantitatively measured),
- movements of migratory individuals, individual movement: travel between seasonal ranges (data: mortality rate, step length, step angle, boundary crossing probability),
- dispersal Success (data: the total number of immigration events of all individuals into all habitat patches).

4. Portfolio of functional criteria

When prioritizing, designing ABMTs and planning coherent networks of these, best criteria and methodologies should be chosen based on the management/conservation goals (conservation priorities) of the area, on the species/habitat present, presence and impacts of human activities, etc, and on different phases of conservation: evaluation of threats/effects, finding and designing conservation strategies, prioritizing management needs and spatially defining the area to be protected and monitoring conservation actions. Here taking inspiration from what Gallagher et al. (2021) have done for traits analysis, we provide a general step by step guidance for the use of functional criteria in a conservation continuum (progression of conservation actions from assessing risk, to designing and prioritizing actions, to implementation and evaluation, Fig. 8). In addition we showcase some hypothetical examples of application for some management questions, which can be of inspiration for test-sites of the MSP4BIO project.

GOALS	Assessing vulnerability/ predicting extinction risks	Designing management strategies/actions	Prioritizing actions	Implementation of conservation actions	Monitoring and evaluation of actions
USE OF CRITERIA	<p><i>Testing for sensitivity and adaptability of species-communities to threats and risk of extinction.</i></p> <p>Traits: capture species responses (vulnerability sensitivity, extinction risks) to threats (e.g. CC)</p> <p>Functional diversity: capture community responses to threats (e.g. CC), etc</p> <p>Trophic ecology: capture resource dependence of one habitat on another, (predicting food webs collapse due to removal of predators/basic resources)</p> <p>Connectivity: capture the level of persistence of populations/species in term of source, sink</p>	<p><i>Creating approaches to effectively mitigate and manage threats to persistence and survival</i></p> <p>Traits: suggest actions for maintaining persistence base of measure of vulnerability and exposure</p> <p>Functional diversity: suggest actions for the maintenance of ecosystem function</p> <p>Trophic ecology: suggest actions for persistence of food webs structure and functioning</p> <p>Connectivity: protecting genetic diversity (gene flow) and the capacity of species to adapt</p>	<p><i>Ranking species communities on their monitoring and management needs</i></p> <p>Traits: help to prioritize most vulnerable species to a threats, and which threat management will delivered the best results</p> <p>Functional diversity: similar as above for entire communities</p> <p>Trophic ecology: define essential trophic relationship for ecosystem functioning</p> <p>Connectivity: consider protection of ecological corridors for migratory species.</p>	<p><i>Spatially prioritizing the implementation of conservation actions</i></p> <p>Traits and Functional diversity: use in mapping exercises on threats to shown exposure to pressure (e.g. to design conservation zone)</p> <p>Trophic ecology: design efficient spatial conservation units based on trophic traits</p> <p>Connectivity: help to spatially define important areas (nurseries, spawning habitats) and migratory routes that allow movements among them.</p>	<p><i>Assessing the success or failure of conservation actions designed to prevent extinctions</i></p> <p>Traits: monitor responses of target species to management actions (e.g. reserve effect, threats removal etc).</p> <p>Functional diversity: monitor responses to management actions on ecosystem functioning</p> <p>Trophic ecology: monitor effect of fishing closure on the whole trophic food webs and functioning (e.g evaluate Fishery-Induced trophic cascades (FITC))</p> <p>Connectivity: monitor effect of management in term of protecting connectivity and gene flow.</p>

Figure 8. General guidance for the use of functional criteria in a conservation continuum whose progressing goals are: assessing risk, designing actions, prioritizing actions, implementation and evaluation (modified from Ghallager et al. 2021).

Tables (3-6) provides a summary of examples of the application of traits based, functional, trophic and connectivity criteria for addressing management/conservation goals, their methods and metrics.

Table 3. Example of application of biological traits criteria for addressing management/conservation goals, and their methods and metrics.

Goals	Methods	Metrics	Usage
<p><i>Protect threatened key species from human and climatic impacts:</i></p> <p>a) Identify which species/population is at risk of extinction</p> <p>b) Delineate critical areas that host most of the species/populations at risk (hotspot of vulnerable species)</p>	<p>Select traits on the base of type of species, threats, conservation/management goals (avoiding redundant traits)</p> <p>Provide literature /experts evaluation to vulnerability traits (provide a vulnerability matrix including traits and threats).</p> <p>Include a quantitative or semiquantitative score for the sensitivity of a species depending on how many traits have been initially selected.</p> <p>Estimate species' exposure to climate change drivers (by combining maps of the projected current distribution for each species and predicted threat/climate change metric)</p> <p>Combine vulnerability indices with exposure</p>	<p>vulnerability, sensitivity indices, exposure indices, combine climate velocity analogues with vulnerability metrics, species risk index provided by the combination of vulnerability and exposure</p>	<p>Assess sensitivity, vulnerability</p> <p>Evaluate potential resilience capacity of species to threats (human and climatic)</p> <p>Predict extinction risks under forecasted scenarios</p> <p>Define conservation plan in light of expected climate changes</p>

Table 4. Example of application of functional diversity criteria for addressing management/conservation goals, and their methods and metrics.

Goals	Methods	Metrics	Usage
<p><i>Protect threatened communities from human and climatic impacts</i></p> <p>a) identify communities at risk of extinction; identify threatened species of particular importance for functional diversity</p> <p>b) predict the potential functional consequences associated with threatened species extinction</p> <p>b) Optimize conservation areas design for protection</p>	<p>Community species traits approach: distribution of species (divided by functional group based on traits and their abundances) in the functional space of a given community. A functional space is a multidimensional space where the axes are functional traits along which species are placed according to their functional trait values.</p>	<p>Functional dissimilarity, Functional divergence, Functional diversity, Functional evenness, Functional identity, Functional originality, Functional richness, Functional specialization</p>	<p>See Moulliot et al. 2013 and section 3.2.2.2 of this deliverable for an in-detail explanation of presented metrics and their usage in conservation.</p>

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Table 5. *Example of application of trophic ecology criteria for addressing management/conservation goals, and their methods and metrics.*

Goals	Methods	Metrics	Usage
Protect ecosystem food web stability and evaluate ecosystem effects of alternative fishing scenarios to explore alternative management strategies	Reconstruction of the food-web structure in the area of interest under alternative scenarios (e.g., fishing vs. not-fishing), and estimation of expected changes in relevant structural and functional food-web features.	Mean trophic level, omnivory, modularity, quasi-sign stability	See Funes et al. (2022) for a simple and clear example of how to reconstruct the food-webs of interest and applied relevant food-web metrics. See section 3.2.2 for an in-detail presentation and description of trophic ecology methods and metrics in the context of conservation and management.

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Table 6. Example of application of connectivity criteria for addressing management/conservation goals, and their methods and metrics. (extracted partially from Balbar and Metaxas, 2019 and literature therein; Burgess et al. 2012).

Goals	Methods	Metrics	Usage
<i>Maintain mobile species persistence (active connectivity)</i>	individual-based modelling, tracking movements (through telemetry tagging methods) or connectivity matrices (i.e., source distribution matrix, e.g.)	Trajectories among habitat (linkage)	Describe trajectories of adults, juveniles, seedlings to highlight linkage among habitats
<i>Maintain population/community persistence (passive connectivity)</i>	modelling to track larval movements (physical dispersion model, lagrangian)	Larval exchange	Evaluate larval exchange between marine habitats and adequate larval supply, and genetic exchange
<i>Maintain local retention/population persistence in MPA</i>	Biophysical dispersal model based on fecundity or survival	Local Retention	Proportion of reproductive output (larvae) that recruits back into the donor population, provides details on replacement and therefore persistence of a population
	Models, reproductive outputs (larvae released)	Source/sink areas	Area of larval source for potential supply of nearby areas
	Observation, (visual census, video recording) eDNA tracking of the presence of a specie	Spillover	E.g., supply of species adult and larvae that can disperse from one protected local area/community to other areas for fisheries harvest outside MPA, in which otherwise it would be excluded by local interactions
<i>connect fragmented landscape (facilitate the transport of biological material)</i>	Observation, (visual census, video recording)	Stepping stone	E.g., small patches used by species to move between large patches, important in fragmented landscapes

	Haplotype diversity, nucleotide diversity, number of haplotype	Isolation by distance, Gene flow, Intraspecific genetic diversity	E.g., parentage analysis, where juveniles can be assigned to their parents and the distance between them can be used to infer the dispersal larval capacities
<i>Selection of planning units (PUs that were not prioritised using habitat data only)</i>	eDNA, Metabarcoding, microsatellites, single-nucleotide polymorphisms, reference genome, genome sequencing	Intraspecific genetic diversity: Genetic clusters, allelic Richness, and local genetic Differentiation. Dispersal	Can help us understand connectivity aspects including gene flow between populations, species sharing genetic material, effective population sizes, and genetic diversity patterns Genome regions affected by natural selection reveal species adaptation and the distribution of beneficial genetic variations, in addition to the defining of species boundaries, which can then be useful to protect endangered species and to design and manage MPAs (van Oppen and Coleman 2022).
	Reconstruction of species-level phylogenetic trees	Phylogenetic diversity	Can be a proxy for functional diversity, and is therefore linked to ecosystem functioning and services
<i>Explore alternative MPA network designs and assess trade-offs of different ecological decisions</i>	R toolbox 'best MPA	Numerous metrics can be used/integrated into the model (Environmental and Economic), e.g. Von Bertalanffy growth model parameters, natural mortality, Larval/adult Dispersal, Stock Biomass, FMSY etc. Please choose from the	The R toolbox BEST MPA (i.e. Bio-Economic Selection Toolbox for Marine Protected Areas) is a "flexible and user-friendly toolkit that focuses on the interaction between MPA network design and population connectivity" (Daigle et al. 2015).

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		following: https://1000research.com/articles/4-1234/v1 and/or https://remidaigle.github.io/BESTMPA/	
<i>Optimize connectivity protecting, implementing and regulating ecological corridors</i>	Marxan + Marxan connect	Many possible metrics, e.g. define betweenness centrality (describes the importance of a node as a connector between different parts of the network) and then choosing a threshold value(s) from the range of the metric." from: https://marxanconnect.ca/tutorial.html	Connectivity incorporated into zonation, provides a graphical user interface to incorporate connectivity matrices and landscape connectivity

Showcase: Northwest Mediterranean Sea

The Ligurian Sea, situated in the northernmost part of the western Mediterranean, has unique characteristics due to its colder waters, leading to a distinct biota with a higher presence of temperate boreal species. This region plays a vital role in the energy balance of the Mediterranean, with strong ocean currents causing upwelling of deep waters (Vietti et al., 2010). This upwelling fosters significant spring primary production, supporting phytoplankton and zooplankton populations. Krill, a primary consumer, plays a key role in the local food web, sustaining large pelagic species like the fin whale, which reproduces in the Ligurian Sea. Importance of Ecosystems and species: Canyons like Bergeggi and Bordighera, located near the coast in the Western Ligurian Sea, often host vulnerable marine ecosystems (VMEs) and habitat-forming species like cold-water corals. These areas are heavily impacted by fishing and marine litter, particularly Derelict Fishing Gears (DFGs) such as nets and ropes, originating from local small-scale trawling fisheries. DFGs reduce coral cover, leading to reduced biodiversity and ecosystem simplification, as well as the ongoing problem of ghost fishing. Trawling also alters seabed sedimentation and morphology in these canyons. The Important Marine Mammal Area (IMMA) Western Ligurian Sea and Genoa Canyon are also located within the Pelagos Sanctuary marine protected area.

The Ligurian Sea, within the Mediterranean, stands out as one of the most heavily influenced areas by human activities. It experiences extensive urbanization, industrial development, tourism, bustling harbor operations, and various construction projects like coastal roads, railways, waste disposal, and drainage systems (Bianchi et al., 2019). The Pelagos Sanctuary is subject to various activities, including military exercises, oil and gas exploration, and seismic surveys, adding to the region's anthropogenic pressures (Fossi et al., 2013). The main threats to this area include the impacts of fishing and shipping, as well as marine litter. Disturbance of species due to human presence, extraction of, or mortality/injury to wild species by commercial and recreational fishing and other activities, input of litter and anthropogenic sound are main threats identified in Annex III MSFD (Marine Strategy Framework Directive).

Table 7. Hypothetical examples of application of functional criteria to prioritize management actions, in response to management questions relevant to MSP4BIO test study case (NW Mediterranean), Pelagos Sanctuary.

Goals/challenges	Criteria	Method	Metrics
<p><i>Reduce impact of sound pollution on key sensitive cetaceans species</i></p> <p><i>Design and adapt conservation areas for the protection of cetacean to noise pollution, particularly during the breeding and feeding season and in sensitive areas</i></p> <p>Annex III MSFD pressures relevant to management goal:</p> <p>Input of anthropogenic sound</p>	<p>Provide information on sensitivity, exposure and vulnerability of species to noise through species traits analysis assess vulnerability index (relevant functional criteria categorized as biological/life traits must be choose based on species and threats)</p> <p>Noises have been documented to affect cetaceans by inducing long-term avoidance of the noisy area, higher energetic costs, stress responses, changes in vocalizations, disruptions in reproduction, foraging, and migration (Bruck 2023).</p> <p>Examples of traits that might be affected: foraging behavior, foraging areas/feeding grounds coverage, juvenile to adult ratio, life history strategy (r/k), mating, nursery area, number of offspring, offspring size, parental care, ratio mature female to male, reproduction rate, reproductive</p>	<p>Observation from whale watching and research vessels, aerial survey, photo ID, video recording, acoustic monitoring, tracking etc.</p> <p>Expert knowledge quantified the relative influence of traits on the vulnerability to noise, give a score to traits</p> <p>compute indexes (exposure to noise, vulnerability)</p> <p>create map of persistence, vulnerability and provide an analysis of overlap with maps of distribution of noise, naval traffic, etc</p>	<p>Exposure, sensitivity, vulnerability to noise</p> <p>Sensitivity is the degree to which marine features respond to a stressor (e.g. behavioral responses to noise or proportional reduction in foraging efficiency due to masking), and vulnerability is the probability that whales are exposed to noise to which they are sensitive.</p>

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	ground, sex ratio, size at sexual maturity, size class, size of offspring, timing of reproductions etc		
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5. Availability of data feeding functional criteria

5.1. Results from the systematic review (D3.1)

The systematic review (D3.1) indicated that 245 articles (57.38% of the total articles selected) did not report data source, whilst the remaining 182 articles (42.62%) reported data originating from a variety of sources (Fig. 9).

Figure 9. Breakdown of the most common data sources used in the screened scientific literature (systematic review, D3.1) to evaluate functional criteria.

Notable mentions are papers with criteria related to the Habitats Directive (HD) comprised of 33 papers (7.73%), NOAA 7 papers (1.64%, e.g. Coral Reef Watch), Water Framework Directive (WFD, directive 2000/60/EC) 6 papers (1.41%), NASA (6 papers, 1.41%) and HELCOM, the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD, directive 2008/56/EC), FishBase and Long Term Ecological Research (LTER) 3 papers each respectively (0.70%). Sources also include data (such as Chlorophyll a, as a proxy for primary productivity) obtained from satellite systems and sensors such as Argos, Google Earth Pro, Copernicus and the Western Mediterranean Operational Forecasting System (WMOP). Data feeding criteria were also provided by/or associated to the International Maritime Organisation (IMO, specifically Particularly Sensitive Sea Areas i.e. PSSAs), WoRMS, EMODnet, GenBank, UNEP World Conservation Monitoring Centre (UNEP-WCMC), Reef Life Survey (hosted by the University of Tasmania), national departments

of fisheries, university depositories and others directly linked to the paper in question or in the cited literature.

In summary, although a large portion of data was not found to be accessible, when functional criteria were available, they can largely be categorized into databases provided by satellite systems, the additional materials of a scientific publication (a large portion of the “Other” category shown in Figure 4 above), EU directives, government agencies and departments, and LTER survey initiatives and repositories run by NGOs, research projects and universities.

5.2. Data availability per cluster of criteria

The table of available datasets and data platforms produced by T2.1 was screened for data relevant to the four main clusters, and possible data gaps were identified. Seventeen datasets and data platforms relating to **traits** were found. These mainly focus on a specific taxonomic group, such as [FishBase](#), [AVONET](#) (birds), and the [Phytoplankton Traits Thesaurus](#), and normally include data on morphological traits, taxonomy, and distribution. One particularly relevant resource is [Marine Species Traits](#), a database of marine species searchable by biological, ecological, taxonomic, and human-defined traits, and integrated with the World Register of marine Species ([WoRMS](#)) and Ocean Biodiversity Information System ([OBIS](#)). Some datasets relating to specific traits were also identified, including [GlobTherm](#), a global database of species’ thermal tolerance, and a [bioturbation classification](#) for marine invertebrates.

No datasets specifically concerning **functional diversity** were found. However, we identified 21 datasets and data platforms on taxonomic diversity which can be used as a proxy, especially when data on traits (see above) is also considered. Major biodiversity data portals include [OBIS](#) and [GBIF](#), and some relevant datasets were also found at the regional or sea basin level, such as [HELCOM’s Biodiversity Database](#) (Baltic Sea) and the Azores’ [Biodiversity Data Portal](#). In addition, 43 datasets and platforms were found to contain data on species distributions and occurrences at a wide range of spatial scales. In a data-poor environment, it may be possible to infer functional diversity using data on species distributions, taxonomic diversity, and/or ecological traits.

Four datasets relating to **trophic ecology** were identified, suggesting a lack of data for this cluster. These datasets were a [global low and mid trophic levels biomass content analysis](#) of zooplankton and micronekton from Copernicus, the EU’s [Marine Ecosystem Assessment](#) of European seas including multiple relevant variables, a global [collection of marine invertebrate traits](#) including trophic guild from the literature, and the [inputs and outputs of a food web model](#) of benthic-pelagic coupling and mixed fisheries in a Mediterranean system (Agnetta et al., 2019). It could be possible to use some species distribution and trait data as a proxy for trophic ecology data. If more data is needed it

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may be found by searching the literature for relevant studies, although such data is not always open access.

Sixteen datasets, models, and tools relating to **connectivity** were found; nine datasets, six models, and one tool. Relatively few datasets containing raw data on connectivity were identified, although the [European Tracking Network data](#) are likely to be highly useful for analysing the connectivity of fish populations. Some data on [larval dispersal](#) were also found and several open-access connectivity models were identified, such as [CMS](#) and [LTRANS](#). [MiCO](#) is a potentially helpful tool to analyse migratory connectivity. However, the availability of data related to reproductive connectivity (e.g. breeding, spawning, and nursery grounds) was low. Since there is a general lack of data on connectivity, seven datasets relating to currents and water velocity were highlighted as possible proxies for plankton connectivity. Forty three datasets relating to species distribution were identified, which could serve as further proxies for connectivity.

6. Link with criteria in use (T2.2, WP2)

Here we provide an exercise to link the screened functional criteria with those indicated by T2.2 (WP2) which have been reported from management actions and environmental policies (Table 8). The scheme matches the terms associated with criteria categories (Fig. 2) with criteria in use. The exercise will be the base to build synergies among criteria to be combined for a more effective protection within the ecological ESE1 module.

Table 8. Summary table of the number of existing criteria and indicators related to the criteria categories.

Categories	Total new criteria	Total criteria	Total biodiversity indicators	International criteria	EU criteria	Mediterranean and Black Sea criteria	OSPAR Region criteria	HELCOM Region criteria
Connectivity	14	48	1	25	3	8	6	6
Functional diversity	30	41	28	27	3	1	6	4
Traits	88	127	111	71	16	12	20	8
Trophic ecology	46	38	31	20	4	7	3	4
Others	11	27	9	6	20	1	0	0

Table 8 summarizes the existing criteria and indicators linked with the new categories from this deliverable. The most represented category is the 'traits' category, also because it contains the highest number of new criteria (88). Compared to European and regional criteria, international criteria are the most relevant to the new criteria. Biodiversity indicators extracted from the DEVOTES database (Texeira et al., 2016) were also linked to the new criteria. These could be relevant for application of the criteria in the planning and management of area-based management tools.

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